

A FRAMEWORK FOR CONDUCTING RISK ANALYSES FOR ALIEN SPECIES IN SOUTH AFRICAN NATIONAL PARKS

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Author biography

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Declaration:

We the Authors of this report declare that the framework presented here is an extension of the "Framework and Guidelines for Conducting Risk Analyses for Alien Taxa" version 1.1 (<https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints201811.0551.v1>) and 1.2 (<https://doi.org/10.3897/neobiota.62.51031>). Permission to reproduce sections of the aforementioned versions of the original framework has been obtained from the authors (Kumschick, Foxcroft & Wilson) and are fully cited. Thus, parts of the questions for information collation and parameters in the report have been copied verbatim from the two versions of the original framework where applicable. Additionally, we declare that this report is not a subsequent version of the original framework but an adjustment to such an extent that the original framework becomes applicable within a setting of a protected area in South Africa. Divergence in application between the framework presented here and the original framework is explicitly explained further in this report.

Abstract

Alien species are essential for human livelihoods and wellbeing, underpinning large sectors of the economy. Alien species also, however, pose a major threat to health, wealth and biodiversity. This is of particular concern in protected areas where the conservation of native biodiversity is often one of the main aims. Since it is not feasible nor desirable to control all alien species, risk analyses are required to formalise the best available evidence of the risks posed by alien species in a manner appropriate for decision makers and managers to decide which species pose an unacceptable level of threat and which should be managed. The framework presented here is based on the latest international developments in the field of risk analysis of biological invasions, and: 1) incorporates recent international frameworks for scoring impacts and classifying introduction pathways; 2) provides a method to facilitate decision-making across species, regions, and realms; 3) explicitly sets up the uncertainty in the underlying assessments; 4) includes information relevant to risk management; and 5) is designed to allow for assessments within capacity and resource constrained environments. The framework presented here is based on, and directly uses parts of, the Risk Analysis for Alien Taxa (RAAT) framework to support alien species regulations (Kumschick, Wilson & Foxcroft, 2020), which was specifically developed for the use in South African national legislative context.

The *Risk Analysis for Alien Species* (RAAS) framework adapts the RAAT framework to meet the needs of management authorities for in protected areas, and South African National Parks specifically. A report written according to RAAS provides decision-makers with information on the risks posed and what can be done to mitigate or prevent impacts, which is necessary for managers of protected areas to decide on the appropriate interventions to implement against alien species. The framework provides a structure for collating relevant data from the published literature to support a robust and transparent process to assess alien species with regards to the need for management, with the aim that it can be completed by a trained science graduate or manager with an environmental/ecological background within a few days. The framework outlines a series of questions related to an alien species' likelihood of invasion, realised and potential impacts, and options for management. The recommendations produced can be used as a first selection for management targets by conducting a robust evaluation of a species, and where results indicate the necessity, further risk management considerations can be developed to prioritise lists of species for control. We discuss the context and structure of the framework, mathematical equations to derive the scores and general recommendations on what the risk management considerations should include. We then apply the RAAS framework to *Cenchrus setaceus* (*Pennisetum setaceum*, fountain grass) in the Kruger National Park.

Keywords: *Cenchrus setaceus*; Decision support; Fountain grass; Impact; Invasive alien species; Protected area; RAAS; Risk assessment; Risk communication; Risk management.

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GLOSSARY

Definitions are based on Blackburn et al. 2011; Kumschick, Wilson & Foxcroft 2017; 2018; Richardson et al. 2000; van Wilgen & Wilson 2018; Zengeya and Wilson 2020.

Alien species: A species in a given area whose presence there is due to intentional or accidental introduction as a result of human activity.

Area: The *Area* of the assessment is defined as the geographic entity under consideration, i.e. the geographic scope of the assessment. In most cases this will be a national park, but can also be only a part of the park. The *Area* may also be defined at a finer scale, for example a river catchment. The region under assessment will be referred to as the *Area* in the framework.

Biological Invasions: The phenomenon of, and suite of processes that are involved in determining the transport of organisms to areas outside their natural range by human activities and the fate of the organisms in their new ranges.

Cultivar: A cultivated variety of a species derived for specific desired characteristics.

Extralimital: A species that has part of their native range in a given country, but whose presence in another part of the same country is attributable to human actions that enabled the taxon to overcome fundamental biogeographical barriers.

Family: A taxonomic group containing one or more genera (e.g. Cactaceae)

Genus: A taxonomic category that ranks above species and below family, and is denoted by a capitalized Latin/scientific name (e.g. *Opuntia*)

Introduction status: Whether a species is found in an area to which it is not native (i.e., where it is alien), and how far along the introduction-naturalisation-invasion continuum it has reached. Ideally presented as per the Blackburn et al. (2011) framework.

Invasive species: A species which is alien to an area and which has self-sustaining populations there with propagules spreading from the initial site of introduction. In other words, an invasive alien species.

Mechanism: A natural process by which something takes place or is driven.

NEMBA A&IS Regulations: The National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act (NEMBA, Act 10 of 2004) Alien and Invasive Species Regulations (Department of Environmental Affairs 2016).

Pathway: The processes by which species are moved between areas.

Primary (introduction) pathway: The combined processes by which species are introduced from one geographical location to another (*cf.* Vector).

Risk analysis: The process of identifying and assessing the likelihood and impact of an event, as well as considerations as to manage and communicate the risks.

Risk assessment: The process of evaluating the likelihood and impact of an event taking place. In this document, such an event would be an alien species becoming a harmful invasive alien species. Risk assessment is part of risk analysis. Risk analysis is comprised of risk assessment, risk management and risk communication.

Risk management: The process of assessing options by which the risks of an event (its likelihood and/or impact) can be reduced or mitigated.

Secondary (dispersal) pathway: The processes by which species disperse or are dispersed from one area of introduction to another.

Sessile species: A species that is attached in one place or is highly immobile and dispersal ability is limited.

Species: A species is a type of organism having certain characteristics that differentiate it from other members of the genus (e.g. *O. stricta*). In the risk analysis framework for SANParks, a "Species" is the entity under assessment, as defined in the Background section of the framework.

Sub-species: A distinct variant, usually based on geographical location, and its name is written *Genus species* subsp. (e.g. *Opuntia stricta* subsp. *stricta*)

Taxon: The taxon under assessment as defined by Kumschick et al. (2020) in the Risk Analysis for Alien Taxa (RAAT) framework from which the risk analysis framework for SANParks is derived. Mostly, this is a species, but can also be a sub-specific entity (e.g., variety, sub-species, etc.) or a different taxonomic level (e.g., a genus).

Variety: See cultivar.

Vector: A mechanism responsible for the transport of species to new areas where they did not previously occur. A pathway (for example shipping) could have several vectors associated with it (for example in cargo, in passenger luggage, on passengers or crew themselves, in ballast water, or attached to the hull).

Propagule: Any spore, seed, fruit, fragment, or other part of an organism capable of reproduction by sexual or asexual means that is dispersed accidentally or deliberately.

1. INTRODUCTION

Species are being moved around the world by humans, both accidentally and deliberately, with the rate of introduction of new species showing few signs of declining (Seebens et al. 2017). Once introduced, some of these species establish and spread without further human assistance. There are also numerous species that were already introduced into an area that will likely become invasive in future. While many alien species are highly beneficial, some can have significant negative impacts on the recipient environment and human livelihoods (Pimentel 2011; Blackburn et al. 2014). This makes management of the most problematic alien species a necessity. However, it is not feasible, nor desirable, to manage all aliens and prioritisation is needed (McGeoch et al. 2016).

1.1. Risk analysis

Kumschick et al. (2020) argue that for successful management and the development of efficient regulations three components are required, namely, risk assessment, risk management and risk communication. While elements of each have been developed in different cases separately (see for example Branquart et al. 2016), the combined information provides a more robust approach. In the context of management of biological invasions, risk assessment consists of the (i) likelihood and consequences of an alien species causing negative impacts (Daehler & Virtue 2010), (ii) risk management deals with options to reduce the risk, including due consideration of potential benefits and (iii) risk communication details how the information is shared between stakeholders (Branquart et al. 2016).

International agreements under the World Trade Organisation (WTO) require the assessment of risks before certain activities involving an alien species, especially trade, can be restricted, or before a new species should be allowed for import. These agreements recognise the standards set by the International Plant Protection Convention (IPPC; FAO 1996) and the World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE 2011). The assessment of the risk that a species poses allows for the distinction between potentially harmful and benign species. However, risk analysis also includes considerations regarding whether and how these risks can be managed (Convention on Biological Diversity 2002). These considerations are fundamental as ignoring management feasibility,

benefits of the species, and potential conflicts between stakeholders, has shown to lead to unsuccessful and wasteful management decisions (e.g. van Wilgen & Richardson 2012). Furthermore, decisions are often only successful and implementable if stakeholders understand the risks associated with the species. To gain the support from the general public, financial institutions and organisations responsible for the implementation of alien species clearing programmes, engagement and clear communication regarding risks is crucial, and this is where risk communication has its place. Furthermore, limited scientific evidence should not hinder action to prevent alien species from becoming problematic or from mitigating their impacts. Therefore, the risk analysis frameworks should be built on the precautionary principle as set out by the Convention on Biological Diversity in their principles related to alien species that threaten ecosystems, habitats or species as outlines in Guiding principle 1 (CBD 2002): "...The precautionary approach should also be applied when considering eradication, containment and control measures in relation to alien species that have become established. Lack of scientific certainty about the various implications of an invasion should not be used as a reason for postponing or failing to take appropriate eradication, containment and control measures".

In order to deal with undesirable impacts and to mitigate future impacts, policy frameworks for the regulation of alien species have been developed for many countries (McGeoch et al. 2010; Early et al. 2016). Such regulations often include lists of species for which certain activities like trade, propagation and movement are prohibited or restricted, and which require mandatory management interventions (Garcia-de-Lomas & Vilà 2015). Decisions on the categorisation of alien species in these lists require a transparent and evidence-based analysis of risk. There are a plethora of schemes that have been developed to address this, but such schemes tend to only focus on particular parts of the problem and are mostly species specific (Leung et al. 2012), and often do not link to probabilities or are not mathematically consistent (Holt 2006; Canessa et al. 2021). Furthermore, risk analyses need to be transparent and repeatable, and align with national and international agreements, policies and best practice (e.g. Roy et al. 2018; Essl et al. 2011; Heikkilä 2011; Kumschick & Richardson 2013; Verbrugge et al. 2010). The challenge is to achieve all these, but be flexible enough to incorporate information from different sources and for the framework to be relevant in different contexts.

1.2. Value of a framework for assessing risk in protected areas

Biological invasions pose a variety of threats (see Pyšek et al. 2020), affecting conservation, biodiversity and people, and most protected areas globally have been invaded or are at risk (see Foxcroft et al. 2013 and chapters therein). Therefore, risk analysis frameworks are needed to explicitly assess and help co-ordinate efforts to manage those risks. Many decision support tools for the management of alien species have been developed (reviewed by Heikkilä 2011; Leung et al. 2012; Kumschick & Richardson 2013).

South African National Parks (SANParks) has listed about 870 alien and extralimital species (Foxcroft et al. 2017), with the costs to the Working for Water/Biodiversity Social Projects totalling about R590 million between 2000/2001 and 2015/2016 (Foxcroft et al. 2017). However, managing all the alien species present is not feasible nor necessary. For example, van Wilgen et al. (2017) suggested that more than one third of the funding spent on managing invasive alien plants in Kruger National Park may have been focused on species of lower importance. A study aimed at elucidating the impacts and pathways of the species of highest concern in SANParks listed 139 'transformer' species (those that change the structure and function of the ecosystem they invade) (Foxcroft et al. 2019) that should receive priority due to the potential negative impacts they pose. Therefore, there is a need to have in place a transparent, robust framework that can be reproduced to assess the risk a species poses to a national park. Threats posed by biological invasions include not only individual alien species, but also invasion pathways, and threats posed collectively to specific areas (CBD 2002; McGeoch et al. 2016).

The RAAT and modified framework for SANParks, takes advantage of the lessons learnt from the application of previous schemes (e.g. Roy et al. 2018) and therefore has several key advantages: 1) it provides a comprehensive structure; 2) it addresses all the aspects of risk analysis in one framework; 3) it is applicable across species and regions. The risk assessment framework therefore provides a transparent and evidence-based tool to underpin policy decisions and to assist in the prioritisation of alien species for management in

providing a first selection of species for further risk management considerations.

Using the RAAT framework (Kumschick, Wilson & Foxcroft 2017; 2018; 2020; Kumschick, Foxcroft & Wilson 2020), which has undergone substantial development and testing by formalising risk analysis in a practical and mathematically sound manner, we believe the Risk Analysis for Alien Species (RAAS) provides a valuable complementary tool for decision makers in SANParks. We adopt the term *Species* rather than *Taxa* as it is more commonly used in SANParks' management plans and other related literature. The RAAS framework can be used to evaluate and highlight priority species both to stop harmful alien species from entering a protected area, and to provide a co-ordinated way of providing the evidence base to justify management interventions for alien species adjacent to, or already present in protected areas.

RAAS incorporates some basic considerations of probabilities by multiplying the likelihood of a species to cross the barriers in the invasion process, i.e. if the species cannot cross a certain barrier (e.g. geographic), the likelihood of establishment is decreased. In reality, each individual likelihood would consist of a range of probabilities, as the exact probability to cross a barrier is difficult to determine. Each assessor would then have to determine which answer is the most suitable for the situation at hand. For ease of calculation, and increased consistency in the application of the framework, we set the upper limit of each range as probability level for the respective answers (e.g. "Probable" equals $p=1$).

Ideally, a risk analysis framework for alien species would recommend the most appropriate management goal for an alien species. However due to the often detailed information needed to set management goals, and the policy and budgetary considerations which need to be included in such decisions, RAAS is not exhaustive in terms of making decisions on which management goal is the most suitable for any species (see also Canessa et al. 2021). Specifically, in isolation RAAS cannot provide recommendations whether a species can be eradicated, and a more detailed analysis is needed to ensure eradication success (e.g. Panetta & Timmins 2004; Wilson et al. 2017). The outcomes of our framework can, however, prioritise or highlight species for which management plans or control targets should be developed. There are several

additional considerations that will need to be made when drafting management plans, for example: stakeholder input is required, including park management, scientists, alien clearing programme managers or tourists; Is it feasible to contain populations? Should asset protection be the main goal of management? Are biocontrol options available? Such issues are important when attempting control, but need to be considered explicitly outside of the RAAS framework should a species be assessed as a high priority.

1.3. A case study for *Cenchrus setaceus* in Kruger National Park: the summary of the risk analysis outcomes

The risk of *Cenchrus setaceus* (*Pennisetum setaceum*, fountain grass) is analysed in this report to illustrate how a risk analysis is conducted using the RAAS framework. *Cenchrus setaceus* is one of the alien species occurring in the Kruger National Park and the surrounding areas. Literature on this *Species* was collated as per the RAAS and the final outcome of the analysis are highlighted in the summary page below (Figure 1).

A summary page provides an overview of the main outcomes of the risk analysis report, though the entire analysis is still required to gain a thorough understanding of the *Species*. The details of the full analyses of the *C. setaceus* assessment are captured in the detailed report (Supplementary material 1), using the report template (Supplementary material 2). The aim of this summary is to provide a concise synthesis of the assessment outcome, which is then presented to relevant managers for further decision making as to what action is appropriate. The summary should ideally not be longer than a page, to enable the reader to rapidly digest the information. Although it is the first page of the analysis report, the summary should be compiled following the completion of a full risk analysis (i.e. section 1-5 of the analysis).

Risk analysis summary

Species: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> (fountain grass)	Area: Kruger National Park (KNP)	
Compiled by: Nkuna, Khensani Vulani	Date of assessment: Date submitted & where:	
Picture of Species <p>https://www.qbif.org/occurrence/search?country=US&has_coordinate=true&has_geospatial_issue=false&taxon_key=5828232</p>		
Risk Assessment summary: Fountain grass (<i>Cenchrus setaceus</i>) was introduced into the Kruger National Park (KNP) as a garden ornamental plant. The savanna biome of the park is a suitable habitat and climatic suitability are met at a large scale. <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> is a fire promoting grass with the potential to transform ecosystems if it becomes invasive. It has been reported to reduce native species richness through direct competition for resources such as soil nutrients, space, and light. It is prolific outside the park along roadsides and other disturbed areas. Spread of <i>C. setaceus</i> is primarily aided by humans intentionally as an ornamental or unintentional as transport stowaway.	Risk score: High	
Management options summary: Any possible socio-economic (ornamental) and environmental (soil stabiliser) benefits of <i>C. setaceus</i> in the park are not considered as they do not contribute to the park's objectives. Populations of <i>C. setaceus</i> in KNP are moderately accessible as they are currently found only in residential areas of the park. However, the propagules (seeds and whole plant) are long-lived and highly persistent, and plants start to reproduce in less than one year which can make management difficult. An eradication feasibility evaluation has not been conducted for the park or other protected areas, but because <i>C. setaceus</i> is widespread outside the park, with large populations in the Phalaborwa region, it is therefore unlikely that eradication is feasible.	Ease of management: Difficult	
Recommended goal: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> is a low priority Species as per the RAAS framework. However, because there are no known invasive populations occurring outside cultivation in the park, it is recommended to control individuals and small populations that might be found in natural areas. Management efforts should be focus on surveillance, especially along the boundaries and buffer zone of the Phalaborwa area. It is also recommend that KNP alien species management engages with relevant authorities outside the park to collaborate in the management of <i>C. setaceus</i> and to encourage measures to prevent entry of the Species into the park.	Listing under NEMBA A&IS regulations 2020: - 1b - Sterile cultivars or hybrids are not listed.	
		KNP Priority level: Low priority

Figure 1: Risk analysis report summary for *Cenchrus setaceus* (fountain grass) in Kruger National Park.

2. THE STRUCTURE OF THE RISK ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK AND PROCEDURE

The following framework is based on the RAAT framework developed for categorising taxa under national legislation (Kumschick et al. 2020) and was adapted to specifically analyse the risk of alien species for National Parks (Risk Analysis for Alien Species - RAAS). Some questions have been modified or rephrased to suit the purpose, and others removed. For instance, terms such as 'taxon' and 'consequences' have been replaced with the terms species and impact, respectively, to align the RAAS with other reports and reporting systems of South African National parks. Where the species under consideration is being referred to in the assessment, it is given as *Species* and similarly with *Area*. The RAAS framework provided here is not a management prioritisation framework, it is a first step in deciding which species need management interventions based on the risk they pose and provides some basic risk management aspects. Further risk management considerations need to be made to prioritise species for management, which are outside of the scope of the RAAS framework. However, we provide an overview of these aspects to illustrate pertinent issues. Once the risk analysis has been completed, the detailed information collated will provide a manager with a comprehensive overview of the species under assessment, which can also be revisited should new information become available.

2.1. Overview of the Risk Analysis for Alien Species (RAAS)

RAAS is divided into five sections and includes all aspects of risk analysis (Figure 2, Table 1), namely risk assessment (Table 7, section 2 and 3), risk management (Table 9 and 11, section 4) and risk communication (Figure 1 and 16, section 1 and 5). The sections are provided with three-letter acronyms (Table 1):

- 1) *Background* (**BAC**) provides information on the assessor, the *Species* under consideration and information needed to perform the analysis;
- 2) *Likelihood* (**LIK**) assesses biological, ecological and behavioural traits of the *Species* that could lead to its arrival, establishment and spread;
- 3) *Impact* (**IMP**) includes the recorded and potential impacts of the *Species*;
- 4) *Risk management* (**MAN**) includes questions related to the ability to control a *Species*, including whether the *Species* is beneficial in some situations,

and provides recommendations for management prioritisation of the *Species*;

- 5) *Reporting* provides guidance on how to communicate the outcomes of the analysis. This last section does not consist of questions, but is a compilation of the results of the previous four sections and provides an easily digestible summary for the communication of recommendations to stakeholders.

		Description	Why?	Parameters	
Risk analysis	Risk communication	1) Background	Provides details of the <i>Species</i> , the <i>Area</i> under assessment, the Assessor and experts consulted	To "set the stage" and ensure transparency, repeatability, and accountability	BAC1 – BAC14
	Risk assessment	2) Likelihood	To collate evidence on aspects which could facilitate entry, establishment and spread	To assess the potential for establishment and invasion	LIK1 – LIK6
		3) Impact	All evidence of possible impacts needs to be collated and scores for environmental and socio-economic impacts	To enable estimation of current and potential severity of impacts	IMP1 – IMP5
	Risk management	4) Management	Available management options are assessed which could mitigate invasiveness and impacts, while preserving benefits	To collate relevant information and gain insights into options for management	MAN1 – MAN5
	Risk communication	5) Reporting	Summarise results of risk assessment and management and provide recommendation for management and regulation	To communicate results clearly and transparently to facilitate debate and reassessment	Summary page

Figure 2: A schematic of the Risk Analysis for Alien Species (RAAS) framework adapted from Kumschick et al. (2020) for South Africa National Parks. For each section a number of parameters needs to be assessed (more detail in Table 1). BAC refers to Background; LIK refers to Likelihood; IMP refers to Impact (i.e. the potential impact of the *Species*); MAN refers to Management (adapted from Kumschick et al. 2020).

Table 1: Definitions and purpose of the parameters or questions and information needed to complete the Risk Analysis for Alien Species (as indicated in Figure 2). BAC refers to Background; LIK refers to Likelihood; IMP refers to Impact; MAN refers to Management.

Questions/ Parameter	Description	Definition and purpose
BAC1	Name of assessor(s)	To identify the person who performed the assessment
BAC2	Contact details of assessor(s)	For means of contacting the assessors in case of questions, further information required, or if the assessment needs revision
BAC3	Name(s) and contact details of expert(s) consulted	Identifies experts which were consulted
BAC4	Scientific name (including the authority) of <i>Species</i> under assessment	Gives information on the species, sub-species, variety, genus, or other taxonomic entity under assessment
BAC5	Synonym(s) considered	Information on which synonyms were considered for the assessment
BAC6	Common name(s) considered	Information on which common names were considered for the assessment
BAC7	What is the native range of the <i>Species</i> ?	Information on the distribution range of the <i>Species</i> is important for the assessment as the framework is designed for alien species specifically
BAC8	What is the global alien range of the <i>Species</i> ?	This is crucial as for some questions, only information in the alien range is considered
BAC9	The <i>Area</i> under consideration	Delimits the geographic scope of the assessment <i>Area</i>
BAC10	Is the <i>Species</i> present in the <i>Area</i> ?	Crucial for management recommendations (e.g. prevention vs. control)
BAC11	Availability of physical specimen	To link the identification of the <i>Species</i> to a physical sample, as it is important to be able to refine the identity (BAC 4) in the light of new information and following <i>Taxonomic</i> revision or the detection of errors in identification
BAC12	Is the <i>Species</i> native to the <i>Area</i> or part of the <i>Area</i> ?	Important for management as this framework only deals with alien species
BAC13	What is the <i>species</i> ' introduction status in the <i>Area</i> ?	Knowing the status of introduction populations (e.g. as per the Unified Framework of Biological Invasions, Blackburn et al. 2011) can aid with management decisions
BAC14	Primary (introduction) pathways	This information will be used to answer questions on likelihood of entry

Questions/ Parameter	Description	Definition and purpose
LIK1	Likelihood of entry via unaided primary pathways	The probability of the <i>Species</i> to arrive and enter the <i>Area</i> without human assistance
LIK2	Likelihood of entry via human aided primary pathways	The probability of the <i>Species</i> to arrive and enter the <i>Area</i> human aided
LIK3	Habitat suitability	Forms part of the likelihood of a <i>Species</i> to establish
LIK4	Climate suitability	Forms part of the likelihood of establishment
LIK5	Unaided secondary (dispersal) pathways	Assesses spread potential
LIK6	Human aided secondary (dispersal) pathways	Assesses spread potential aided by humans
IMP1	Environmental impact	Includes impacts caused by the <i>Species</i> on the environment through different mechanisms, based on EICAT (IUCN 2020)
IMP2	Socio-economic impact	Includes impacts caused by the <i>Species</i> on human well-being and livelihood, based on SEICAT (Bacher et al. 2018)
IMP3	Closely related species' environmental impact	If no data on the <i>Species</i> itself is available, this includes impacts caused by related species on the environment through different mechanisms
IMP4	Closely related species' socio-economic impact	If no data on the <i>Species</i> itself is available, this includes impacts caused by related species on different socio-economic sectors
IMP5	Potential impact	Assesses the potential impact of the <i>Species</i> in the <i>Area</i> if invasive
MAN1	What is the feasibility of stopping future introductions into the <i>Area</i> ?	Important for effectiveness of control, as new influx of propagules needs to be stopped to control the <i>Species</i> effectively and sustainably
MAN2	Benefits of the <i>Species</i>	Socio-economic and environmental benefits are included to assess the needs of stakeholders related to the <i>Species</i>
MAN3	Ease of management	To provide indication of how easy the <i>Species</i> is to manage in the <i>Area</i> as this will influence risk management decisions
MAN4	Has the feasibility of extirpation or eradication been evaluated?	Indicates whether the feasibility of eradicating or extirpating the <i>Species</i> from the <i>Area</i> , or other SANParks, or other similar protected areas (e.g. a protected area with similar habitat or in the same biome) has been formally evaluated. Note the evaluation of eradication feasibility is a separate process to the risk analysis framework

Questions/ Parameter	Description	Definition and purpose
MAN5	What is the range size of the <i>Species</i> in the <i>Area</i> ?	Important for prioritisation of the <i>Species</i> for the evaluation of control feasibility Estimate the range size of the <i>Species</i> within KNP (or immediately adjacent), as the distinction between the range sizes is important to distinguish between High and Medium levels of priority. <i>Species</i> that are potentially difficult to manage are considered low priority regardless of their range size.
MAN6	What are the control options and management actions available for the <i>Species</i> ?	Provides an overview of management interventions and options available to control the <i>Species</i> in the <i>Area</i>
MAN7	Any other management considerations to highlight?	This is intended to support decision making, so a critical evaluation of options (including those that are not suitable) is useful, but it should ideally be backed up with appropriate referencing. It might also include information useful for management prioritisation or that might ultimately end up in a species-specific management plan.
Appendix BAC7	A map of the <i>native range</i>	This map indicates the native range of the <i>Species</i> under assessment.
Appendix BAC8	A map of the <i>global alien range</i>	Indicates the extent of the <i>Species</i> outside its native range.
Appendix BAC10	A map of the <i>alien range in the Area</i>	Indicates the extent of the <i>Species</i> within the <i>Area</i> under assessment.
Appendix MAN7	Other management considerations that need to be highlighted	Highlights other aspects to be considered during management prioritisation. This includes aspects about the <i>Area</i> or the <i>Species</i> (congeners, cultivars, etc.) under assessment.

2.2. Assessing risk and confidence of data/ results

Risk analysis provides a valuable tool for collating and synthesising knowledge to produce insight into a particular scenario. However, the outcome of the analysis is dependent on the data and attention to detail that is exercised in the process. A thorough literature review on the species should be conducted to find all relevant information. The literature review remains valid if a species is evaluated for different parks, as only the implication of the results will change (e.g. habitat suitability). If no information is published on the *Species*,

closely related species should be considered, for example congeners. If this is the case, it needs to be clearly indicated in the comments of the respective questions where such information was used. Experts on the *Species* should be consulted, especially if the *Species* is data deficient or data are not readily available, including indigenous and local knowledge where the *Species* is native. Some information can be extracted from national and international databases on native and alien species, e.g. the Global Invasive Species Database, Global Biodiversity Information Facility, and the Red List of Threatened Species. A list of potential sources of information can be found in Appendix 1. Experience from multiple risk assessments conducted (e.g. see Kumschick et al. 2020) shows that the assessment is best performed by an assessor with a Master's level degree or someone trained in using the RAAS framework. This is due to familiarity with searching and working with primary scientific literature and suitable grey literature, and extracting and interpreting relevant information. It is also, however, possible to assess the respective species in expert groups, for example through workshops and working groups.

Unless otherwise specified, each question should have one answer out of the response options provided (in the Response box on the Answer sheet), with a corresponding estimate of the confidence in the answer, in the Confidence box on the Answer sheet, see Guidance on confidence scoring. In each case, a short description on why the response was chosen must be provided in the Rationale/Comments section on the answer sheet, including names of experts consulted for the respective questions, a summary of the main sources of information, and citations that were used to help answer the question. It is acceptable to copy and paste information directly from the sources, given these are properly referenced and put in inverted commas. List relevant references used for each question in the References section, providing the full reference including authors, year, title, journal (if applicable), issue and page numbers, and a web-links for websites (e.g. a digital object identifier (doi) for books, databases, and journal articles) including date of access, and the name and contact details of experts who provided input into specific questions, including links to the databases or information if possible.

The confidence score should give an indication regarding the certainty of the answer, in other words, how confident the assessor is that the answer provided is correct. This generally depends on the amount and quality of data available on the *Species*. Guidance on confidence rating is based on the EPPO

pest risk assessment decision support scheme (Hawkins et al. 2015) (Section 2.4.5).

2.3. Scope of analysis

The region under assessment is referred to as the *Area* in the remainder of the document and in the framework (see BAC9). In most cases assessments will be done on the level of a single national park (e.g. Kruger National Park), but can be done at a smaller scale as needed. The only criterion is that the *Area* is clearly specified.

The *Species* under assessment can be a species (e.g. *C. setaceus*), sub-species, genus or any other taxonomic level. Risk analyses are mostly carried out on individual species, but this is not always appropriate, e.g. if the taxonomy of a group is not well resolved; if species are difficult to distinguish but the whole group (i.e., genus or family) is of potential concern (e.g. certain invertebrate plant pests like mites or rust fungi); and if there are important differences between sub-species.

2.4. The risk analysis model

To ensure the outcome of the risk analysis is robust and defensible, the data collected through the literature search are used to populate a model to provide scores or indices that can indicate potential scenarios. The model is calculated on the basis of the (i) likelihood and (ii) impacts (potential impacts), from which the likelihood and impact scores are used to calculate the (iii) Risk Assessment score. The management feasibility (iv) is calculated separately. The calculation of *C. setaceus* for each stage informs the summary page above.

2.4.1. Likelihood of the *Species* becoming invasive

The questions in this section represent the invasion process, with two questions for each step in the process (i.e. entry, establishment and spread). Figure 3 illustrates the model for how the final Likelihood score is calculated from the answers provided in questions LIK1–LIK6. The Likelihood description can be transcribed into a probability level *p* value as in Table 2, which are

entered into Table 3 to calculate a final likelihood of an invasion occurring (**Eq.1**, Figure 3). The final likelihood score feeds into the Risk assessment (Table 7).

The likelihood assessment of *C. setaceus* indicates a probable (1) score for LIK1 and LIK2 as the *Species* already occurs and has naturalised in KNP. The likelihood of spread is lower due to the restrictions and inhibition of intentional introductions of alien species into the park (See supplementary material 1, section 2 for the full assessment). The final score (likelihood of invasion) for *C. setaceus* in KNP is therefore fairly probable (Table 4).

Table 2: Transcription of Final Likelihood scores into the probability levels p of invasion of the species.

Likelihood (description)	Likelihood score (p)	Description
Extremely unlikely	≤ 0.000001	As likely as winning the lottery, if you play it once.
Very unlikely	$0.000001 < p \leq 0.0027$	As likely as a new person you meet having their birthday on the same day as yours.
Unlikely	$0.0027 < p \leq 0.027$	As likely as rolling two sixes when playing dice.
Fairly probable	$0.027 < p \leq 0.5$	As likely as getting heads when flipping a coin, i.e. fifty-fifty.
Probable	$p > 0.5$	More likely to happen than not / definitely going to happen

Table 3: The likelihood scores of the *Species* to enter, establish, and spread in the Area (see also Figure 3 and Table 2). The likelihood of the *Species* to become invasive is calculated as follows:

$$P(\text{invasion}) = \text{Max}(\text{LIK1}, \text{LIK2}) * \text{Max}(\text{LIK3}, \text{LIK4}) * \text{Max}(\text{LIK5}, \text{LIK6}) \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

Parameter	Likelihood score	Stages <small>Maximum likelihood per stage</small>	Final assessment <small>$P(\text{invasion}) = P(\text{entry}) * P(\text{establishment}) * P(\text{spread})$</small>
LIK1		P (entry) =	P (invasion) =
LIK2			
LIK3		P (establishment) =	
LIK4			
LIK5		P (spread) =	
LIK6			

Table 4: The likelihood of invasion for *C. setaceus* in KNP indicating a fairly probable (0.5) score (see supplementary material 1 for more details).

Likelihood of invasion = fairly probable (0.5)

Parameter	Likelihood	Stages Maximum likelihood per stage	Final assessment $P(\text{invasion}) = P(\text{entry}) * P(\text{establishment}) * P(\text{spread})$
LIK1	1	P(entry) = 1	P (invasion) = 0.5
LIK2	1		
LIK3	1	P(establishment) = 1	
LIK4	1		
LIK5	0.5	P (spread) = 0.5	
LIK6	0.027		

Figure 3: Calculation of the final likelihood score (likelihood of invasion) based on LIK1-LIK6.

2.4.2. Impacts of the Species

The impact scores are based upon environmental impacts, socio-economic impacts and potential impacts (Figure 4). The results from IMP1– IMP5 are used to calculate maximum impact levels for the *Species*. For the impact score, the maximum impact level is taken between all the impact measures (IMP1– IMP5). This impact level is then used to calculate the impact score as described in Table 5. The levels for the impact assessment in the risk assessment are based on Hawkins et al. (2015; Environmental impact), Bacher et al. (2018; Socio-economic impact) and Kumschick et al. (2020;

Potential impact). These are rated as Massive (MV), Major (MR), Moderate (MO), Minor (MN), and Minimal Concern (MC). Where IMP1 and IMP2 are Data Deficient (DD), IMP3 and IMP4, respectively, must be used.

The impact assessment indicate that *C. setaceus* pose major environmental impact through direct competition with native species and minimal socio-economic impact (Table 6). The assessment also indicates that invasion of *C. setaceus* in KNP has the potential to reduce grazing capacity and ultimately reduces nutrition for grazers as it is unpalatable with low nutritional value. The maximum impact score for *C. setaceus* is therefore Major (MR) (See supplementary material 1, section 3 for more details).

Figure 4: Model to determine the maximum impact scores.

Table 5: Environmental and Socio-economic impact scores for the *Species* under assessment

Parameter	Mechanism/sector	Response
IMP1a	Competition	
IMP1b	Predation	
IMP1c	Hybridisation	
IMP1d	Disease transmission	
IMP1e	Parasitism	

IMP1f	Poisoning/toxicity	
IMP1g	Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance	
IMP1h	Grazing/herbivory/browsing	
IMP1i	Chemical, physical, structural impact	
IMP1k	Indirect impacts through interactions with other species	
IMP1	Maximum environmental impact	
IMP2a	Safety	
IMP2b	Material and immaterial assets	
IMP2c	Health	
IMP2d	Social, spiritual and cultural relations	
IMP2	Maximum socio-economic impact	
IMP3	Environmental impact of closely related species [not scored if IMP1 is scored]	
IMP4	Socio-economic impact of closely related species	
IMP5	Potential impact based on traits, experiments, or models	

Table 6: Environmental and socio-economic impact Scores of *C. setaceus* in KNP.

Final score = Major (MR)

Parameter	Mechanism/sector	Response
IMP1a	Competition	MR
IMP1b	Predation	NA
IMP1c	Hybridisation	MC
IMP1d	Disease transmission	DD
IMP1e	Parasitism	NA
IMP1f	Poisoning/toxicity	DD
IMP1g	Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance	DD
IMP1h	Grazing/herbivory/browsing	NA
IMP1i	Chemical, physical, structural impact	MO
IMP1k	Indirect impacts through interactions with other species	MN
IMP1	Maximum environmental impact	MR
IMP2a	Safety	MC
IMP2b	Material and immaterial assets	DD
IMP2c	Health	MC
IMP2d	Social, spiritual and cultural relations	MC
IMP2	Maximum socio-economic impact	MC
IMP3	Environmental impact of closely related species	Not scored as IMP1 scored
IMP4	Socio-economic impact of closely related species	Not scored as IMP2 scored
IMP5	Potential impact based on traits, experiments, or models	MO

2.4.3. Assessing risk (Likelihood X Impact)

The maximum impact score (Table 5, Figure 4, section 3) together with the likelihood of invasion (Table 3, Figure 3, section 2), are used to assess the level of risk as low, medium or high in Table 7. Regardless of whether the risk is low and no prioritised management is likely to be recommended, the entire assessment needs to be completed in the same way the assessment would be completed for medium and high risk species. The risk assessment in the case study indicates that *C. setaceus* is a high-risk species for KNP due to the fairly probable likelihood of invasion and the major impact score (Table 8).

Table 7: The Risk assessment score, based on the Likelihood of invasion (Table 3) and the maximum impact score (Table 5).

		Impact				
		MC	MN	MO	MR	MV
Likelihood	Extremely unlikely	low	low	low	medium	medium
	Very unlikely	low	low	low	medium	high
	Unlikely	low	low	medium	high	high
	Fairly probable	medium	medium	high	high	high
	Probable	medium	high	high	high	high

Table 8: Risk score of *C. setaceus* for KNP based on the outcomes of the Likelihood score (fairly probable) and the overall impact score (Major).

RISK SCORE = High

		Impacts				
		MC	MN	MO	MR	MV
Likelihood	Extremely unlikely	low	low	low	medium	medium
	Very unlikely	low	low	low	medium	high
	Unlikely	low	low	medium	high	high
	Fairly probable	medium	medium	high	high	high
	Probable	medium	high	high	high	high

2.4.4. Management

Some basic risk management questions are evaluated here. For the species which are shown to be high risk and which result in a higher priority category,

a more detailed management feasibility study could be conducted, for example, as suggested by Booy et al. (2017; 2020). While the scheme by Booy et al. (2017; 2020) does not prioritise species for eradication, it can aid in the prioritisation process, based on risk management considerations.

Risk assessment scores are not necessarily related to extirpation eradication (management) feasibility scores. This indicates that a second step in management prioritisation, especially those designated as potential eradication targets would be an eradication feasibility assessment. This step may be conducted by relevant park management or Working for Water/Biodiversity Social Projects, who are responsible for implementation of the control programmes. Various data collected during the RAAS assessment may be useful in an eradication feasibility study as it provides background on the target species and some management information from the management related questions (Table 9).

The *Species'* ease of management is based on the accessibility of populations, detectability of the *Species*, time of reproduction, and propagule persistence (MAN3a–MAN3d). These four aspects are then summed up to determine the ease of management as either 'easy, medium, or difficult' (Table 10).

The case study indicates that *C. setaceus* can reproduce in less than one year, individual plants may live up to 20 years, and seeds may remain viable in the soil for six to seven years, and is in flower for at least nine months of the year (see supplementary material 1, section 4 for more detailed). These traits of *C. setaceus* can make management of *C. setaceus* in KNP difficult to control and manage in the long-term (Table 11).

Table 9: Summary of questions for assessing ease of management

Parameter	Question	Response
MAN1	What is the feasibility to stop future introduction into the <i>Area</i> ? (e.g. adjacent to the park, entire park, specially delineated sections of the park)	High/Low
MAN2a	Socio-economic benefits of the <i>Species</i>	High/Low
MAN2b	Environmental benefits of the <i>Species</i>	High/Low
MAN3a	How accessible are populations?	0 for easy access. 1 for moderately accessible. 2 for difficult to access; or don't know.

MAN3b	Is the <i>Species</i> hard to detect?	0 for no. 1 for partially or for most of the year. 2 for yes; or only detectable for a few weeks a year; or don't know.
MAN3c	Time to reproduction	0 for > 3 years. 1 for 1–3 years; or don't know. 2 for < 1 year.
MAN3d	Propagule persistence	0 for < 1 year. 1 for 1–5 years; or don't know. 3 for > 5 years.
MAN3	SUM of MAN3a—MAN3d	>5: Difficult. Generally difficult to manage. 3–5: Medium. Some aspects make it more difficult to manage. <3: Easy. Management is relatively straightforward.
MAN4	Has the feasibility of extirpation or eradication been evaluated in the <i>Area</i> , other SANParks, or similar protected areas (ideally with similar habitat or in the same biome) that may provide insights for the <i>Area</i> being assessed?	Yes: there has been a detailed evaluation of extirpation/eradication feasibility that has been documented (e.g. in a journal article). No: there has been no evaluation of extirpation/eradication for the <i>Area</i> or a different region.
MAN5	What is the range size of <i>Species</i> in the <i>Area</i> ?	<10 %: Small range size ≥10 % but ≤20 %: Medium range size >20 %: Large range size
MAN6	What are the control options and management actions available for the <i>Species</i> ?	Management actions: monitoring, prevention, eradication, control or none/unknown Control options: biocontrol, herbicide control, electrofishing, rotenone

MAN7	Any other management considerations to highlight? Any additional information that can be provided is important to assist managers and policy makers in decision making.	Yes: details are provided in appendix MAN7 No: no appendix is not provided
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Table 10: The ease of management score of the *Species* under assessment

Parameter	Question	Response/Score
MAN3a	How accessible are populations?	
MAN3b	Is the <i>Species</i> hard to detect?	
MAN3c	Time to reproduction	
MAN3d	Propagule persistence	
MAN3	SUM of MAN3a—MAN3d	

Table 11: Ease of management for *C. setaceus* in KNP.

Ease of management = difficult (6)

Parameter	Question	Response/Score
MAN3a	How accessible are populations?	1
MAN3b	Is the <i>Species</i> hard to detect?	0
MAN3c	Time to reproduction	2
MAN3d	Propagule persistence	3
MAN3	SUM of MAN3a—MAN3d	6

2.4.5. Reporting risk and management recommendations

The decision tree (Figure 5) is used to determine the *Species* level of priority using results and scores obtained in the likelihood, impact, and ease of management section. The priority level and the recommended goal are then communicated in the risk communication sections (Table 16, sections 5). The final outcomes are also summarized on the first page of the risk analysis report to provide an easily digestible summary for the communication of recommendations to stakeholders.

The final outcome of the case study suggest low priority level for *C. setaceus* in KNP. This is because although *C. setaceus* pose is high-risk for KNP based on the likelihood of invasion and maximum impact, management of the *Species* can be difficult. Therefore it is recommended that efforts should be focused on other risk management aspects such as surveillance of new introductions and other long-term control programs (see also Figure 1 for the risk analysis summary and supplementary material 1 for the full risk analysis report). It is also important for management that the species is correctly identified in the field, for example, there may be native *Pennisetum* spp. that resemble *C. setaceus*.

Figure 5: A decision tree to determine the priority level and risk management response for the *Species* under assessment. The information in brackets refers to question numbers in the RAAS framework.

2.5.6. Confidence rating

The confidence level is determined based on the amount and 'quality' of information/data available to support an answer in the assessment. The RAAT framework adopted a confidence rating scheme modified from the EPPO pest risk assessment decision support scheme (Hawkins et al. 2015), and is similarly adopted here.

High confidence (approximately 90% chance of the response / assessment being correct):

- There is direct relevant observational evidence to support the assessment;
- and Impacts are recorded at the typical spatial scale over which original native communities can be characterized;
- and There are reliable/good quality data sources on impacts of the species;
- and The interpretation of data/information is straightforward;
- and Data/information are not controversial or contradictory.

Medium confidence (approximately 65-75% chance of the response / assessment being correct):

- There is some direct observational evidence to support the assessment, but some information is inferred;
- and/or Impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which may not be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, but extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered reliable, or to embrace little uncertainty;
- and/or The interpretation of the data is to some extent ambiguous or contradictory.

Low confidence (approximately 35% chance of the response / assessment being correct)

- There is no direct observational evidence to support the assessment, e.g. only inferred data have been used as supporting evidence;
- and/or Impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which is unlikely to be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, and extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered unreliable or to embrace significant uncertainties.

- and/or Evidence is poor and difficult to interpret, e.g. because it is strongly ambiguous.
- and/or The information sources are considered to be of low quality or contain information that is unreliable.

2.5. Data sources

Some useful data sources to answer certain questions are given in Appendix 1. The scientific literature should be taken into account, and primary sources used and cited where possible. However, databases on alien species contain large amounts of useful information on many species as well and may be consulted. This table is not an inclusive list of all potential sources which can and should be considered for risk analyses, and it does not replace the reference list which needs to be provided by the assessor as support for answering the questions outlined in the framework.

3. QUESTIONS AND DESCRIPTIONS OF EACH SECTION OF THE ASSESSMENT

3.1. Background information for the assessment

As indicated above, the background gives important information on the assessor, the *Area*, and the *Species*. The questions are described here in detail (Table 12). For each question a section in the Answer sheet template (Supplementary material 2) needs to be filled, generally consisting of Response, Confidence, Comments/Rationale, and References. Unless otherwise stated, all these sections need to be filled in. See the glossary for terms used in the framework.

Table 12: Questions to collate background information of the *Species* under assessment

BAC question number	Question / information required
<i>BAC1 Name of assessor(s)</i>	Give the full name and surname of the main assessor and any additional assessors. The lead assessor takes responsibility for the assessment and is the author/assessor for correspondence. Add more lines if more assessors were involved.
<i>BAC2 Contact details of assessor(s)</i>	Add more lines if more assessors were involved.
<i>BAC3 Name(s) and contact details of expert(s) consulted</i>	This can include internal (e.g. within SANParks or BSP, or groups of assessors) or external (including international) experts or reviewers, which influenced, commented or amended the document. In the comments, outline the kind of contribution these experts made. Add additional lines if several experts were consulted.
<i>BAC4 Scientific name of Species under assessment</i>	The biological entity under consideration. The full scientific (binomial) name as well as taxonomic authority is required. In most cases, this will be a species, but it could be another taxonomic level (e.g. genus or sub-species). Mention the taxonomic level under comments. The organism under assessment will be called the " <i>Species</i> " in the rest of the document. Check ITIS (http://www.itis.gov/) or a <i>Species</i> specific taxonomic database for the correct nomenclature, and note the validity of the name under comments. Note in the references which database was used for the species identification/name. Please ensure the currently adopted name is used.
<i>BAC5 Synonym(s) considered</i>	List synonyms of the scientific (Latin) name of the <i>Species</i> which were considered for this assessment. Only list names included in the literature search, not synonyms which were not considered. Check for synonyms in ITIS (http://www.itis.gov/) or a <i>Species</i> specific taxonomic database. Note in the references which database was considered.

<p>BAC6 <i>Common name(s) considered</i></p>	<p>List common names of the <i>Species</i> which were considered for this assessment. Only list names included in the literature search, not all recorded common names. In the comments, indicate where the common names are used, and which languages were considered.</p>
<p>BAC7 <i>What is the native range of the Species?</i></p>	<p>The <i>Species</i>' biogeographic distribution provides useful context for understanding the actual and potential range of the <i>Species</i>. Here, a description in words is required, which can aid the literature search.</p> <p>If the <i>Species</i>' native range includes other areas in South Africa, the <i>Species</i> should be clearly listed as extralimital.</p> <p>A map of the native range should be provided, if possible. If the map is available in a file, please insert a low res copy (<1MB) as an appendix to the Answer sheet and provide the file name and (if possible) a link to a higher resolution copy.</p>
<p>BAC8 <i>What is the global alien range of the Species?</i></p>	<p>This includes the <i>Species</i>' global alien range, including the range within the <i>Area</i>. The distribution of the <i>Species</i>' introduced range provides useful context for understanding the actual and potential range of the <i>Species</i> and provides guidance for the literature search.</p> <p>A map of the alien range should be provided, if possible. If the map is available in a file, please insert a low res copy (<1MB) as an appendix to the Answer sheet and provide the file name and (if possible) a link to a higher resolution copy.</p>
<p>BAC9 <i>Geographic scope = the Area under consideration</i></p>	<p>Specify the geographic entity under consideration, i.e. the geographic scope of the assessment. In most cases this will be a specific National Park, but can also be the whole country, a single province, or a river catchment. The region under assessment will hereafter be referred to as the "<i>Area</i>". The <i>Species</i> should generally only be assessed in its alien range.</p>
<p>BAC10 <i>Is the Species present in the Area?</i></p>	<p>Note if the <i>Species</i> is present anywhere in the <i>Area</i>. In the case where the presence of the species is not confirmed but a record has been noted, include field visits, as appropriate.</p> <p>A map of the <i>Area</i> indicating the extent of the invasion should be provided, if possible. If the map is available in a file, please insert a low res copy (<1MB) as an appendix to the Answer sheet and provide the file name and (if possible) a link to a higher resolution copy.</p> <p>Images of the <i>Species</i> captures in the <i>Area</i> should also be provided in the Appendix.</p>
<p>BAC11 <i>Availability of physical specimen</i></p>	<p>In the Response, state if a physical sample was collected in the <i>Area</i> (yes/no). The name of the herbarium/museum and its accession number / record of the <i>Species</i> in the <i>Area</i> should be provided in the respective section. The record should have been checked by a national and/or international <i>Taxonomic</i> expert, and the person at the herbarium/museum who identified the sample and date should also be given. A GPS coordinates may be also be used only if the identification of the <i>Species</i> has been verified by an expert or a reliable data source.</p> <p>If the <i>Species</i> has not previously been reported as present in the <i>Area</i> and the identity is not certain OR if no herbarium or museum record is available, contact a relevant specialist. Record all information that can be</p>

	obtained from the specialist; including a reference to some herbarium or museum, so that in the future if need be it will be possible to determine what the <i>Species</i> ' identity was compared to at the initial identification, i.e. if it turns out in future that the identification could be wrong, we need to be able to understand why it was identified as that particular <i>Species</i> .
<i>BAC12 Is the Species native to the Area or part of the Area?</i>	Indicate whether the <i>Species</i> is alien or extralimital (occurs elsewhere in South Africa; BAC7) and select one of the answers provided for each (yes, no, or don't know). If alien to the whole or parts of the <i>Area</i> , clarify under BAC7 that only alien ranges are considered for this assessment.
<i>BAC13 What is the Species' introduction status in the Area?</i>	<p>If the <i>Species</i> is present in the <i>Area</i>, define its introduction status as follows (according to Blackburn et al. 2011):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - alien in cultivation/captivity: individuals transported beyond the limits of its native range and in captivity, quarantine or cultivation, i.e., individuals provided with conditions suitable for them, but explicit measures of containment or explicit measures to prevent spread are in place - alien outside of cultivation/captivity: individuals transported beyond the limits of native range and directly released into the new environment, or individuals escaped from cultivation/captivity, but incapable of surviving for a significant period or, if surviving in the wild, no reproduction or, if reproduction occurring, population not self-sustaining - established: individuals surviving outside of cultivation/captivity in locations where introduced, reproduction occurring, and population self-sustaining - invasive: self-sustaining populations outside of cultivation/captivity with individuals surviving and reproducing a significant distance from the original point of introduction, i.e. dispersal happening. <p>Give information on each step in the invasion continuum and select one of the answers provided for each (yes, no, or don't know).</p>
<i>BAC14 Primary (introduction) pathways</i>	List historical, currently known and potential future entry pathways for the <i>Species</i> in the <i>Area</i> and other introduced ranges. See Appendix 2 for suggested pathway categories and subcategories. The pathway categories are based on the one accepted by the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (see also Essl et al. 2011), and aligns with the Pathway Controlled Vocabulary List of Terms

3.2. Risk Assessment

The risk posed by an alien *Species* is divided into i) the *likelihood* the *Species* will become invasive (Table 13) and ii) the impacts resulting from the introduction of the *Species* (Table 14).

3.2.1. Likelihood

The section on likelihood assesses the probability of the *Species* to enter, establish and spread in the *Area*. This generally represents the stages in the invasion process (Blackburn et al. 2011), with two questions for each stage, resulting in six questions in total (LIK1–LIK6 in Table 13). Each answer is expressed as a probability value p , with all the levels and scenarios described in the narrative section, and each level representing an order of magnitude difference. If the answer is unknown after consulting the literature and experts, following a precautionary principle the answer is treated as $p=1$ (highest probability) for the rest of the assessment, though noting that no answer was supplied and so highlighting an obvious area where more research is needed (Hulme 2012). For each probability level we give general examples which assessors could experience or identify with to provide guidance.

These are structured as follows:

- Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): as likely as winning the lottery if you play it once.
- Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): as likely as a new person you meet having their birthday on the same day as yours.
- Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): as likely as rolling two sixes when playing dice.
- Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): as likely as getting heads when flipping a coin, i.e., fifty-fifty.
- Probable ($p = 1$): more likely to happen than not / definitely going to happen.

Table 13: Questions, response options and probability of the Likelihood of the *Species* becoming invasive in the *Area*.

LIK question number	Question / information required AND response options
<p>LIK1 <i>Likelihood of entry via unaided primary pathways</i></p>	<p>If the <i>Species</i> is present in the <i>Area</i> (see BAC10), the probability of entry should be set as 1. Still fill in this section as if the <i>Species</i> was not present and give details on pathways, as this can inform risk management and the feasibility to stop future immigration or spread. However, for the calculations use the probability of 1.</p> <p>Estimate the probability that the <i>Species</i> enters the <i>Area</i> from outside the <i>Area</i> through unaided pathways within the timespan of a decade. Consider the unaided pathways mentioned under BAC14. Features of the <i>Species</i> which favour unaided entry include presence in neighbouring countries and regions, water or wind dispersed propagules (e.g. floating propagules), the ability to fly long distances, the ability for fish to move from one river catchment where introduced, to another via connected waterways. Animal dispersal is also considered here, except domestic and farm animals which are included under LIK2. The following factors can aid entry via animals: edible parts (e.g. fruits) which are eaten by animals, propagules with spines/barbs/sticky substances which can attach to animals, very small propagules which can get stuck in fur and feathers, pests attached to plants or animals. List the pathways and corresponding likelihoods in the comments section. In the response, give the highest likelihood for any pathway. The assessment should be based on the likelihood of entry based on current and future pathways.</p> <p><i>Response options:</i></p> <p>Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): the <i>Species</i> and its propagules are highly sessile and are known never to disperse on its own – proof is required for inability to move, otherwise classify as “Very unlikely”.</p> <p>Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): the <i>Species</i> and its propagules are sessile and do not usually disperse on their own</p> <p>Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): the <i>Species</i> is sessile, but it can disperse or be dispersed during one specific life stage, dispersal capabilities are slow and short distance</p> <p>Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): the <i>Species</i> is highly mobile during at least one of its life stages and can reach a high dispersal capability during one of its life stages</p> <p>Probable ($p = 1$): highly mobile <i>Species</i> with dispersal capability fast and over large distances</p> <p>Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on the unaided pathways available to the <i>Species</i></p>
<p>LIK2 <i>Likelihood of entry via human aided</i></p>	<p>If the <i>Species</i> is present in the <i>Area</i> (see BAC10), the probability of entry should be set as 1. Still fill in this section as if the <i>Species</i> was not present and give details on pathways, as this can inform risk management and the feasibility to stop future immigration. However for the calculations, use the probability of 1.</p>

<p><i>primary pathways</i></p>	<p>Estimate the probability that the <i>Species</i> enters the <i>Area</i> from outside the <i>Area</i> through the pathways mentioned under BAC14 which are human mediated (as opposed to unaided, which are covered in LIK1) within the timespan of a decade. List the pathways and corresponding likelihoods in the comments section. This also includes entry from neighbouring countries (consider it could in future be introduced into neighbouring countries). In the response, give the highest likelihood for any pathway. The assessment should be based on the likelihood of introductions based on current and future pathways. For species which are already present in the <i>Area</i>, mainly focus on unintentional pathways.</p>
	<p><i>Response options:</i></p> <p>Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): There is currently no human aided entry pathway available/in use for the <i>Species</i>, and no future pathway is expected to arise</p> <p>Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): There is currently a human aided entry pathway available/in use, but the <i>Species</i> is highly sensitive to movement and is unlikely to arrive alive at any life stage</p> <p>Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): There is a human aided entry pathway available/in use which is infrequently used, and/or future new pathways are expected to arise; also, the <i>Species</i> is not expected to arrive in high numbers</p> <p>Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): Several human aided entry pathways are available/in use but not regularly used, and/or some potentially lead to a high number of introductions</p> <p>Probable ($p = 1$): Several human aided entry pathways available and regularly used for the <i>Species</i>, and high numbers of individuals expected.</p> <p>Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on the human aided pathways used by the <i>Species</i></p>

<p>LIK3 <i>Habitat suitability</i></p>	<p>Indicate the likelihood of the <i>Species</i> to find suitable habitats in the <i>Area</i> for survival and reproduction. Habitat includes the presence of suitable food items, hosts, pollinators, seed dispersers, and other biotic conditions. If the <i>Area</i> encompasses multiple habitats, consider those that are most likely suited and mention in the comments section which habitats were assessed. Thus also take the habitat specificity of the <i>Species</i> into account. Artificial habitats include for example gardens or landscaped camps for plants or birds, artificial dams or in-stream weirs.</p> <p><i>Response options:</i> Extremely unlikely ($p < 0.000001$): the <i>Species</i> is extremely specialised and there is no suitable habitat in the <i>Area</i>, none of the key conditions for the <i>Species</i>' survival are met Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): the <i>Species</i> is highly specialised, but there is reason to assume that it might adapt to some biotic habitat conditions; only highly artificial habitats which are rare or difficult to maintain are suitable. Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): the <i>Area</i> provides habitat that is only partly suitable to the <i>Species</i>; certain artificial habitats are suitable Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): the key conditions are met, but only in a marginal part of the <i>Area</i>; also non-artificial habitats suitable. Probable ($p = 1$): all key biotic habitat conditions are met in a large part of the <i>Area</i>. Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on habitat requirements of the <i>Species</i></p>
<p>LIK4 <i>Climate suitability</i></p>	<p>Indicate the likelihood of the <i>Species</i> to find suitable climate in the <i>Area</i> for survival and reproduction. Use the native and alien ranges as references for the <i>Species</i>' distribution, as obtained in BAC7 and BAC8. As a minimal standard, use published maps of climate zones to check whether the climate in the <i>Area</i> is suitable for the <i>Species</i>. Such maps include the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Koeppen-Geiger climate zones, updated by Peel et al. (2007) - Richardson and Thuiller (2007) maps of global locations that match South African climates <p>Climate models are more desirable and lead to a higher confidence in the assessment.</p> <p>If the <i>Area</i> encompasses multiple climate zones, consider those that are most likely suited and mention in the comments section which climatic zones were assessed. For species already present in the <i>Area</i>, the answer cannot be "extremely unlikely".</p> <p><i>Response options:</i> Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): The <i>Area</i> provides no suitable climate (including artificially created environments) Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): The <i>Area</i> provides no suitable climate, but suitable climate can be artificially created in small (<5%) parts of the <i>Area</i>.</p>

	<p>Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): The <i>Area</i> provides little (<5%) climatic overlap with the known distribution of the <i>Species</i>, excluding artificially created suitable habitats.</p> <p>Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): The main climatic requirements are met in a marginal (>5% but <20% - one fifth) part of the <i>Area</i>.</p> <p>Probable ($p = 1$): The main climatic requirements are met in a larger part (>20%) of the <i>Area</i>.</p> <p>Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on the climatic requirements of the <i>Species</i></p>
<p>LIK5 <i>Unaided secondary (dispersal) pathways</i></p>	<p>This includes the unaided pathways currently or potentially bringing the <i>Species</i> from the occupied regions to elsewhere within the <i>Area</i>. It excludes unaided pathways bringing propagules from areas outside of the <i>Area</i> into the <i>Area</i> (covered in LIK1). Indicate the probability that the <i>Species</i> disperses naturally from a population within the <i>Area</i> to currently unoccupied regions and habitats. Mention details of the expected dispersal pathways and mechanisms in the comments section. More precisely, try to estimate the probability that the <i>Species</i> can disperse > 50 km in a decade. Features of the <i>Species</i> which favour unaided dispersal include water or wind dispersed propagules (e.g. floating propagules), the ability to fly long distances, the ability for fish to move from one river catchment where introduced, to another via connected waterways. Animal dispersal is also considered here, except domestic and farm animals which are included under LIK6. The following factors can aid dispersal by animals: edible parts (e.g. fruits) which are eaten by animals, propagules with spines/barbs/sticky substances which can attach to animals, very small propagules which can get stuck in fur and feathers, pests attached to plants or animals.</p> <p><i>Response options:</i></p> <p>Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): the <i>Species</i> and its propagules are highly sessile and are known never to disperse on their own or unaided by humans – proof is required for inability to move, otherwise classify as “Very unlikely”.</p> <p>Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): the <i>Species</i> and its propagules are sessile and do not usually disperse on their own or unaided by humans</p> <p>Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): the <i>Species</i> is sessile, but it can disperse during one specific life stage, dispersal capabilities are slow and short distance (< 50km in 10 years)</p> <p>Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): the <i>Species</i> is mobile and can reach a high dispersal capability during one of its life stages</p> <p>Probable ($p = 1$): highly mobile <i>Species</i> with dispersal capability fast and over large distances</p> <p>Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on unaided dispersal pathways used by the <i>Species</i></p>
<p>LIK6 <i>Human aided secondary (dispersal) pathways</i></p>	<p>This includes the human aided pathways currently or potentially bringing the <i>Species</i> from the occupied regions and habitats elsewhere within the <i>Area</i>. This question does not include dispersal from outside of the <i>Area</i> to the <i>Area</i> as this is covered in LIK2. Indicate the probability that the <i>Species</i> gets dispersed from a population within the <i>Area</i> to uninvaded habitats. Intentional and unintentional pathways need to be considered. Mention details of the expected pathways in the comments section. The</p>

	<p>likelihood score relates to the proximity of the <i>Species</i> to human and domestic/farm animals and frequency of contact, which allows it to be dispersed in these kinds of dispersal pathways, as well as traits and features of the <i>Species</i> which facilitate for it to be moved around. More precisely, try to estimate the probability that human-mediated dispersal takes (propagules of) the <i>Species</i> > 50 km in a decade. Features of the <i>Species</i> which favour human aided dispersal include edible parts (e.g. fruits), propagules with spines/barbs/sticky substances which can attach to clothing, vehicles and boats, building materials, very small propagules which can get stuck in clothing/shoes or with movement of ornamental plants and be transported unnoticed. Dispersal by domestic and farm animals is included here.</p> <p><i>Response options:</i></p> <p>Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): the <i>Species</i> is not present in places accessible by humans, domestic and/or farm animals</p> <p>Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): the <i>Species</i> is only present in places humans, domestic and/or farm animals can reach with difficulty, and/or has no features which make it likely to be dispersed human aided</p> <p>Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): the <i>Species</i> is present in places where humans, domestic and/or farm animals occasionally occur, and/or has features which make it possible to be dispersed human aided, but only exceptional cases</p> <p>Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): the <i>Species</i> is present in places easily accessible by humans and/or it or its propagules are easily moved, i.e. it possesses some feature mentioned above</p> <p>Probable ($p = 1$): the <i>Species</i> is present in a place frequented by humans, and it or its propagules are easily and regularly moved due to features mentioned above</p> <p>Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on the human aided pathways used by the <i>Species</i></p>
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3.2.2. Impacts

The impacts section is specifically detailed as it is important to gain a comprehensive understanding of the potential harm caused by an alien *Species*. Importantly, both environmental and socio-economic impacts are included in the risk assessment (e.g. Kumschick & Richardson 2013; Roy et al. 2018). The assessment of current and potential impacts here is based on recent developments of impact scoring schemes (Blackburn et al. 2014; Nentwig et al. 2016; Bacher et al. 2018). The Environmental Impact Classification of Alien Taxa (EICAT) is used for the assessment of environmental impacts (Blackburn et al. 2014, Hawkins et al. 2015). It has been adopted by the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN) as a standard for the classification of alien species (IUCN 2020), to be used alongside the Red List for the conservation of biodiversity. For

socio-economic impacts, a scoring scheme that is more closely aligned to EICAT, and more consistent in the way impact levels are assigned is used, namely the Socio Economic Impact Classification of Alien Taxa (SEICAT) (Bacher et al. 2018).

In this section, all evidence of impacts in the global alien range (including the *Area*) available for the *Species* needs to be collated and scored for environmental impacts and socio-economic impacts. Data on the impacts of the *Species* itself from the *Area* or other alien regions are the most desirable (IMP1a–IMP1k and IMP2a–IMP2f). Only if no data are available on the *Species* in any alien range globally should it be classified as Data Deficient (DD) under IMP1 and IMP2. For mechanisms which do not apply to a specific *Species*, also note DD. If this is the case, i.e. no data are available for the *Species* on impacts anywhere in its global alien range, search for data of congeners or other closely related species with similar life history traits and fill in IMP3 and IMP4.

Additionally data from the native range of the *Species* may be considered, and/or estimate the magnitude of impact possible for the *Species* in the *Area* based on biological, ecological and behavioural traits (in IMP5). This needs to be captured regardless of whether information on CON1 and IMP2 is available, but can lead to similar results if the impact of the *Species* has been well studied.

Capture all results as described below (Table 14) from IMP1-IMP5 into section 3 of the answer sheet and calculate the maximum impact levels for the *Species*. For the impact score, the maximum impact level should be taken between all the impact measures. This impact level is then used to calculate the risk score as described in Table 7.

Table 14: Environmental and socio-economic impact assessment questions, mechanisms, and response options based of the EICAT and SEICAT.

IMP question number	Question / information required
IMP1 <i>Environmental impact</i>	Assess the environmental impact of the <i>Species</i> in its global alien range (i.e. everywhere it has been introduced outside of its native range). Fill in the Answer sheet for each of the mechanisms as described below (IMP1a-IMP1k). Then use the scheme provided in Figure 4 to calculate the environmental impact score (IMP1), which is basically the maximum of all the mechanisms. Report on the maximum impact found in any of the mechanisms for the global alien range in the Response for IMP1, and

	<p>the main mechanism affected in the Rationale, but provide information on all the sectors and impact scores in IMP1a)-IMP1k), including detailed information on the references used for the assessments. If impact assessments have been conducted previously for the Taxon and are available in the literature, information can be extracted from there and no detailed search is needed.</p> <p>If no data on impact are available for the Taxon anywhere in the global alien range for any of the mechanisms described, mark the Taxon as Data Deficient (DD) here and additionally fill in IMP3, i.e. consider information on closely related taxa.</p>
IMP1a Competition	<p>What is the evidence in the global alien range of the <i>Species</i> for impact through competition?</p> <p>Does the <i>Species</i> compete with native taxa for resources (e.g. food, water, or space), leading to deleterious impact on native taxa somewhere in its global alien range?</p> <p>Classify the <i>Species</i> in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).</p> <p>Response options:</p> <p>Massive (MV) Competition resulting in replacement or local extinction of one or several native taxa; changes are irreversible</p> <p>Major (MR) Competition resulting in local population extinction of at least one native <i>Species</i>, but changes are reversible when the alien <i>Species</i> is no longer present</p> <p>Moderate (MO) Competition resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native <i>Species</i>, but no local population extinction</p> <p>Minor (MN) Competition affects performance of native individuals without decline of their populations</p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) Negligible level of competition with native taxa; reduction of performance of native individuals is not detectable</p>
IMP1b Predation	<p>This consists of the <i>Species</i> preying on native taxa somewhere in its global alien range, and includes direct effects leading to deleterious impact on native taxa.</p> <p>Classify the <i>Species</i> in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).</p> <p>Response options:</p> <p>Massive (MV) Predation results in local extinction of one or several native taxa; changes are irreversible</p> <p>Major (MR) Predation results in local population extinction of at least one native <i>Species</i>; reversible when the alien <i>Species</i> is no longer present</p> <p>Moderate (MO) Predation results in a decline of population size of at least one native <i>Species</i>, but no local population extinction</p> <p>Minor (MN) The alien <i>Species</i> preys on native taxa, without leading to a decline in their populations</p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) Not applicable; predation on native taxa is classified at least as MN.</p>
IMP1c Hybridisation	<p>The <i>Species</i> hybridises with native species somewhere in its global alien range, leading to deleterious impact on native species.</p> <p>Classify the <i>Species</i> in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).</p>

	<p>Response options:</p> <p>Massive (MV) Hybridisation between the alien <i>Species</i> and native taxa leading to the loss of at least one pure native population (genomic extinction); pure native taxa cannot be recovered even if the alien and hybrids are no longer present</p> <p>Major (MR) Hybridisation between the alien <i>Species</i> and native taxa leading to the loss of at least one pure native population (genomic extinction); reversible when the alien <i>Species</i> and hybrids are no longer present</p> <p>Moderate (MO) Hybridisation between the alien <i>Species</i> and native taxa is regularly observed in the wild; local decline of populations of at least one pure native <i>Species</i>, but pure native taxa persist</p> <p>Minor (MN) Hybridisation between the alien <i>Species</i> and native taxa is observed in the wild, but rare; no decline of pure local native populations</p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) No hybridisation between the alien <i>Species</i> and native taxa observed in the wild, hybridisation with a native <i>Species</i> is possible in captivity</p>
<p>IMP1d <i>Transmission of disease</i></p>	<p>The <i>Species</i> transmits diseases to native species somewhere in its global alien range, leading to deleterious impact on native species. Classify the <i>Species</i> in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).</p> <p>Response options:</p> <p>Massive (MV) Transmission of disease to native taxa resulting in local extinction of at least one native <i>Species</i>; changes are irreversible</p> <p>Major (MR) Transmission of disease to native taxa resulting in local population extinction of at least one native <i>Species</i>; reversible when the alien <i>Species</i> is no longer present</p> <p>Moderate (MO) Transmission of disease to native taxa resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native <i>Species</i>, but no local population extinction; disease is severely affecting native taxa, including mortality of individuals, and it has been found in native and alien co-occurring individuals (same time and space)</p> <p>Minor (MN) Transmission of disease to native taxa affects performance of native individuals without leading to a decline of their populations; alien <i>Species</i> is a host of a disease which has also been detected in native taxa and affects the performance of native taxa</p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) The alien <i>Species</i> is a host or vector of a disease transmissible to native taxa but disease not detected in native taxa; reduction in performance of native individuals is not detectable</p>
<p>IMP1e <i>Parasitism</i></p>	<p>The <i>Species</i> parasitises native species somewhere in its global alien range, leading directly or indirectly (e.g. through apparent competition) to deleterious impact on natives. Classify the <i>Species</i> in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).</p> <p>Response options:</p> <p>Massive (MV) Parasites or pathogens directly result in local extinction of one or several native taxa; changes are irreversible</p> <p>Major (MR) Parasites or pathogens directly result in local population extinction of at least one native <i>Species</i>, but changes are reversible when the alien <i>Species</i> is no longer present</p>

	<p>Moderate (MO) Parasites or pathogens directly result in a decline of population size of at least one native <i>Species</i>, but no local population extinction</p> <p>Minor (MN) Parasites or pathogens directly affect performance of native individuals without decline of their populations</p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) Negligible level of parasitism or disease incidence (pathogens) on native taxa, reduction in performance of native individuals is not detectable</p>
<p>IMP1f <i>Poisoning/ toxicity</i></p>	<p>The <i>Species</i> is toxic, or allergenic by ingestion somewhere in its global alien range, inhalation or contact to wildlife, or allelopathic to plants, leading to deleterious impact on native species. Classify the <i>Species</i> in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).</p> <p>Response options:</p> <p>Massive (MV) The alien <i>Species</i> is toxic/allergenic by ingestion, inhalation, or contact to wildlife or allelopathic to plants, resulting in local extinction of at least one native <i>Species</i>; changes are irreversible</p> <p>Major (MR) The alien <i>Species</i> is toxic/allergenic by ingestion, inhalation, or contact to wildlife or allelopathic to plants, resulting in local population extinction of at least one native <i>Species</i>, but changes are reversible when the alien <i>Species</i> is removed</p> <p>Moderate (MO) The alien <i>Species</i> is toxic/allergenic by ingestion, inhalation, or contact to wildlife or allelopathic to plants, resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native <i>Species</i>, but no local population extinction</p> <p>Minor (MN) The alien <i>Species</i> is toxic/allergenic by ingestion, inhalation, or contact to wildlife or allelopathic to plants, affecting performance of native individuals without decline of their populations</p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) The alien <i>Species</i> is toxic/allergenic/allelopathic, but the level is very low, reduction of performance of native individuals is not detectable</p>
<p>IMP1g <i>Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance</i></p>	<p>The accumulation of individuals of the <i>Species</i> on wetted surfaces leads to deleterious impact on native species somewhere in its global alien range. Classify the <i>Species</i> in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).</p> <p>Response options:</p> <p>Massive (MV) Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance resulting in local extinction of one or several native taxa; changes are irreversible</p> <p>Major (MR) Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance resulting in local population extinction of at least one native <i>Species</i>, but changes are reversible when the alien <i>Species</i> is no longer present</p> <p>Moderate (MO) Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native <i>Species</i>, but no local population extinctions</p> <p>Minor (MN) Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance affects performance of native individuals without decline of their populations</p>

	<p>Minimal Concern (MC) Negligible level of bio-fouling or direct physical disturbance on native taxa; reduction in performance of native individuals is not detectable</p>
<p>IMP1h <i>Grazing/ herbivory /browsing</i></p>	<p>Grazing, herbivory or browsing by the <i>Species</i> leads to deleterious impact on native plant species somewhere in its global alien range. Classify the <i>Species</i> in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).</p> <p>Response options:</p> <p>Massive (MV) Herbivory/grazing/browsing resulting in local extinction of one or several native taxa; changes are irreversible</p> <p>Major (MR) Herbivory/grazing/browsing resulting in local population extinction of at least one native <i>Species</i>, but changes are reversible when the alien <i>Species</i> is no longer present</p> <p>Moderate (MO) Herbivory/grazing/browsing resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native <i>Species</i>, but no local population extinction</p> <p>Minor (MN) Herbivory/grazing/browsing affects performance of individuals of native taxa without decline of their populations</p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) Negligible level of herbivory/grazing/browsing on native taxa, reduction in performance of native taxa is not detectable</p>
<p>IMP1i <i>Chemical, physical or structural impact on ecosystem</i></p>	<p>The <i>Species</i> causes changes to either: the chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics of the native environment; nutrient and/or water cycling; disturbance regimes; or natural succession, leading to deleterious impact on native species somewhere in the <i>Species</i>' global alien range. Classify the <i>Species</i> in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).</p> <p>Response options:</p> <p>Massive (MV) Changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient and water cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession, resulting in local extinction of at least one native <i>Species</i>; changes are irreversible</p> <p>Major (MR) Changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession, resulting in local extinction of at least one native species, changes are reversible when the alien <i>Species</i> is no longer present</p> <p>Moderate (MO) Changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession, resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native <i>Species</i>, but no local population extinction</p> <p>Minor (MN) Changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession detectable, affecting performance (e.g. growth, reproduction, defence, immunocompetence) of native individuals without decline of their populations</p>

	<p>Minimal Concern (MC) Small changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession detectable, but no reduction of performance of native individuals</p>
<p>IMP1k <i>Indirect impacts through interactions with other species</i></p>	<p>The <i>Species</i> interacts with other (native or alien) taxa, (e.g. through pollination, seed dispersal, habitat modification, mesopredator release), facilitating deleterious impact on native species somewhere in its global alien range.</p> <p>Classify the <i>Species</i> in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).</p> <p>Response options</p> <p>Massive (MV) Interaction of an alien <i>Species</i> with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g. pollination, seed dispersal, habitat modification, apparent competition) causing local extinction of one or several native taxa, leading to irreversible changes that would not have occurred in the absence of the alien <i>Species</i></p> <p>Major (MR) Interaction of an alien <i>Species</i> with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g. pollination, seed dispersal, habitat modification, apparent competition) causing local population extinction of at least one native <i>Species</i>; changes are reversible but would not have occurred in the absence of the alien <i>Species</i></p> <p>Moderate (MO) Interaction of an alien <i>Species</i> with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g. pollination, seed dispersal, habitat modification, apparent competition) causing a decline of population size of at least one native <i>Species</i>, but no local population extinction; impacts would not have occurred in the absence of the alien <i>Species</i></p> <p>Minor (MN) Interaction of an alien <i>Species</i> with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g. pollination, seed dispersal, apparent competition) affecting performance of native individuals without decline of their populations; impacts would not have occurred in the absence of the alien <i>Species</i></p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) Interaction of an alien <i>Species</i> with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g. pollination, seed dispersal, apparent competition) but reduction in performance of native individuals is not detectable</p>
<p>IMP2 <i>Socio-economic impact</i></p>	<p>Assess the socio-economic impact of the <i>Species</i> in its global alien range (i.e. everywhere it has been introduced outside of its native range).</p> <p>This concerns impacts on the following constituents of human well-being:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) safety (b) material and immaterial assets (c) health (d) social, spiritual and cultural relations <p>Fill in the Answer sheet for each of the constituents of human well-being (IMP2a-IMP2d), and use Figure 4 to calculate the main socio-economic impact score. Report on the maximum impact found in any of the constituents of human well-being and any alien range in the Response to IMP2, and the main sector affected in the Rationale, but provide information on all the sectors and impact scores in IMP2a)-2d), including detailed information on the references used for the assessments.</p>

	<p>If no data on impact are available for the <i>Species</i> in any part of its alien range globally on any of the sectors described below, mark the <i>Species</i> as Data Deficient (DD) here and additionally fill in IMP4.</p>
<p>IMP2a Safety</p>	<p>This concerns impacts on human well-being affecting activities related to safety, for example personal safety and secure resource access (e.g. to open access hiking areas where invaded sites might create security concerns), security from disasters (e.g. dense invasions of plants in river areas leading to damage). Classify the <i>Species</i> in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).</p> <p>Massive (MV) Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Species</i> affecting aspects of human safety. Change is likely to be permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien <i>Species</i>, due to fundamental structural changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions (“regime shift”)</p> <p>Major (MR) Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Species</i> affecting aspects of human safety. Collapse of the specific social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without replacement, or emigration from region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien <i>Species</i>. “Local disappearance” does not necessarily imply the disappearance of activities from the entire region assessed, but refers to the typical spatial scale over which social communities in the region are characterised (e.g. multi land use protected areas)</p> <p>Moderate (MO) Negative effects on well-being leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but the activity is still carried out. Reductions in activity size can be due to various reasons, e.g. moving the activity to regions without the alien <i>Species</i> or to other parts of the area less invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>; partial abandonment of an activity without replacement by other activities; or switch to other activities while staying in the same area invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>. Also, spatial displacement, abandonment or switch of activities does not increase human well-being compared to levels before the alien <i>Species</i> invaded the region (no increase in opportunities due to the alien <i>Species</i>)</p> <p>Minor (MN) Negative effect on peoples’ well-being, such that the alien <i>Species</i> makes it difficult for people to participate in their normal activities. Individual people in an activity suffer regarding safety. Reductions of well-being can be detected through e.g. income loss, health problems, higher effort or expenses to participate in activities, increased difficulty in accessing goods, disruption of social activities, induction of fear, but no change in activity size is reported, i.e. the number of people participating in that activity remains the same</p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) No deleterious impacts reported despite availability of relevant studies with regard to its impact on human well-being. Taxa that have been evaluated under the SEICAT process but for which impacts have not been assessed in any study should not be classified in this category, but rather should be classified as data deficient</p>

	<p>Data Deficient (DD) There is no information to classify the <i>Species</i> with respect to its impact, or insufficient time has elapsed since introduction for impacts to have become apparent</p>
<p>IMP2b <i>Material and immaterial assets</i></p>	<p>This concerns impacts on human well-being affecting activities leading to changes in the availability and quality of tangible and intangible assets, for example adequate livelihoods, sufficient nutritious food, shelter, access to goods. Classify the <i>Species</i> in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).</p> <p>Massive (MV) Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>. Change is likely to be permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien <i>Species</i>, due to fundamental structural changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions (“regime shift”)</p> <p>Major (MR) Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>. Collapse of the specific social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without replacement, or emigration from region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien <i>Species</i>. “Local disappearance” does not necessarily imply the disappearance of activities from the entire region assessed, but refers to the typical spatial scale over which social communities in the region are characterised (e.g. a human settlement)</p> <p>Moderate (MO) Negative effects on well-being leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but the activity is still carried out. Reductions in activity size can be due to various reasons, e.g. moving the activity to regions without the alien <i>Species</i> or to other parts of the area less invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>; partial abandonment of an activity without replacement by other activities; or switch to other activities while staying in the same area invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>. Also, spatial displacement, abandonment or switch of activities does not increase human well-being compared to levels before the alien <i>Species</i> invaded the region (no increase in opportunities due to the alien <i>Species</i>)</p> <p>Minor (MN) Negative effect on peoples’ well-being, such that the alien <i>Species</i> makes it difficult for people to participate in their normal activities. Individual people in an activity suffer in at least one constituent of well-being (i.e. security; material and non-material assets; health; social, spiritual and cultural relations). Reductions of well-being can be detected through e.g. income loss, health problems, higher effort or expenses to participate in activities, increased difficulty in accessing goods, disruption of social activities, induction of fear, but no change in activity size is reported, i.e. the number of people participating in that activity remains the same</p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) No deleterious impacts reported despite availability of relevant studies with regard to its impact on human well-being. Taxa that have been evaluated under the SEICAT process but for which impacts have not been assessed in any study should not be classified in this category, but rather should be classified as data deficient</p> <p>Data Deficient (DD) There is no information to classify the <i>Species</i> with respect to its impact, or insufficient time has elapsed since introduction for impacts to have become apparent</p>

<p>IMP2c <i>Health</i></p>	<p>This includes impacts on human well-being affecting their health, and, including access to clean air and water. For IAPs, the case of <i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> (parthenium/famine weed) in Kruger, which is known to cause human health impacts, such as contact dermatitis, asthma or bronchitis, and animal health impacts. Classify the <i>Species</i> in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).</p> <p>Massive (MV) Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>. Change is likely to be permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien <i>Species</i>, due to fundamental structural changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions (“regime shift”)</p> <p>Major (MR) Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>. Collapse of the specific social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without replacement, or emigration from region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien <i>Species</i>. “Local disappearance” does not necessarily imply the disappearance of activities from the entire region assessed, but refers to the typical spatial scale over which social communities in the region are characterised (e.g. a human settlement)</p> <p>Moderate (MO) Negative effects on well-being leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but the activity is still carried out. Reductions in activity size can be due to various reasons, e.g. moving the activity to regions without the alien <i>Species</i> or to other parts of the area less invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>; partial abandonment of an activity without replacement by other activities; or switch to other activities while staying in the same area invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>. Also, spatial displacement, abandonment or switch of activities does not increase human well-being compared to levels before the alien <i>Species</i> invaded the region (no increase in opportunities due to the alien <i>Species</i>)</p> <p>Minor (MN) Negative effect on peoples’ well-being, such that the alien <i>Species</i> makes it difficult for people to participate in their normal activities. Individual people in an activity suffer in at least one constituent of well-being (i.e. security; material and non-material assets; health; social, spiritual and cultural relations). Reductions of well-being can be detected through e.g. income loss, health problems, higher effort or expenses to participate in activities, increased difficulty in accessing goods, disruption of social activities, induction of fear, but no change in activity size is reported, i.e. the number of people participating in that activity remains the same</p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) No deleterious impacts reported despite availability of relevant studies with regard to its impact on human well-being. Taxa that have been evaluated under the SEICAT process but for which impacts have not been assessed in any study should not be classified in this category, but rather should be classified as data deficient</p> <p>Data Deficient (DD) There is no information to classify the <i>Species</i> with respect to its impact, or insufficient time has elapsed since introduction for impacts to have become apparent</p>
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<p>IMP2d Social, spiritual and cultural relations</p>	<p>This concerns impacts on human well-being affecting social, spiritual and cultural relations, for example social, spiritual and cultural practice, mutual respect, and which can be linked to loss of heritage sites, damage to picnic sites, open access or communal zones (e.g. hiking or fishing). Classify the <i>Species</i> in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).</p> <p>Massive (MV) Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>. Change is likely to be permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien <i>Species</i>, due to fundamental structural changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions (“regime shift”)</p> <p>Major (MR) Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>. Collapse of the specific social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without replacement, or emigration from region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien <i>Species</i>. “Local disappearance” does not necessarily imply the disappearance of activities from the entire region assessed, but refers to the typical spatial scale over which social communities in the region are characterised (e.g. a human settlement)</p> <p>Moderate (MO) Negative effects on well-being leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but the activity is still carried out. Reductions in activity size can be due to various reasons, e.g. moving the activity to regions without the alien <i>Species</i> or to other parts of the area less invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>; partial abandonment of an activity without replacement by other activities; or switch to other activities while staying in the same area invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>. Also, spatial displacement, abandonment or switch of activities does not increase human well-being compared to levels before the alien <i>Species</i> invaded the region (no increase in opportunities due to the alien <i>Species</i>)</p> <p>Minor (MN) Negative effect on peoples’ well-being, such that the alien <i>Species</i> makes it difficult for people to participate in their normal activities. Individual people in an activity suffer in at least one constituent of well-being (i.e. security; material and non-material assets; health; social, spiritual and cultural relations). Reductions of well-being can be detected through e.g. income loss, health problems, higher effort or expenses to participate in activities, increased difficulty in accessing goods, disruption of social activities, induction of fear, but no change in activity size is reported, i.e. the number of people participating in that activity remains the same</p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) No deleterious impacts reported despite availability of relevant studies with regard to its impact on human well-being. Taxa that have been evaluated under the SEICAT process but for which impacts have not been assessed in any study should not be classified in this category, but rather should be classified as data deficient</p> <p>Data Deficient (DD) There is no information to classify the <i>Species</i> with respect to its impact, or insufficient time has elapsed since introduction for impacts to have become apparent</p>
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<p>IMP3 Environmental impact of closely related species</p>	<p><i>This section is only considered if the Response is Data Deficient (DD) in IMP1.</i></p> <p>Consider here data of congeners or other closely related taxa with similar life history traits and their environmental impacts in their global alien range. In detail, perform a classification of impacts as described in IMP1a-IMP1k for closely related and similar taxa. Note which taxa was/were considered in the Rationale, and report on the details of the different impact mechanisms on the Answer sheet. In the Response to IMP3, note the maximum impact found in any mechanism.</p> <p>Environmental impact</p> <p>Massive (MV) Causes local extinction of at least one native <i>Species</i> (i.e., taxa vanish from communities at sites where they occurred before the alien arrived), which is irreversible; even if the alien <i>Species</i> is no longer present the native <i>Species</i> cannot recolonize the area</p> <p>Major (MR) Causes local or sub-population extinction of at least one native <i>Species</i> (i.e., taxa vanish from communities at sites where they occurred before the alien arrived); which is reversible if the alien <i>Species</i> is no longer present</p> <p>Moderate (MO) Causes population declines in at least one native <i>Species</i>, but no local population extinctions</p> <p>Minor (MN) Causes reductions in individual performance (e.g. growth, reproduction, defence, immunocompetence), but no declines in local native population sizes</p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) Negligible level of impacts; no reduction in performance (e.g. growth, reproduction, defence, immunocompetence) of individuals of native taxa</p>
<p>IMP4 Socio-economic impact of closely related species</p>	<p><i>This section is only considered if the Response is Data Deficient (DD) in IMP2.</i></p> <p>Consider here data of congeners or other closely related taxa with similar life history traits and their socio-economic impacts in their global alien range. More specifically, perform a classification of impacts as described in IMP2a-IMP2d for closely related and similar taxa. Note which taxa was/were considered in the Rationale, and report on the details of the different sectors on the Answer sheet. In the Response to IMP4, note the maximum impact found on any sector.</p> <p>Socio-economic impact</p> <p>Massive (MV) Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>. Change is likely to be permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien <i>Species</i>, due to fundamental structural changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions (“regime shift”)</p> <p>Major (MR) Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Species</i>. Collapse of the specific social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without replacement, or emigration from region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien <i>Species</i>.</p> <p>Moderate (MO) Negative effects on well-being leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but the activity is still carried out.</p>

	<p>Minor (MN) Negative effect on peoples' well-being, such that the alien <i>Species</i> makes it difficult for people to participate in their normal activities. Individual people suffer in at least one constituent of well-being (i.e. security; material and non-material assets; health; social, spiritual and cultural relations).</p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) No deleterious impacts reported despite availability of relevant studies with regard to its impact on human well-being</p>
<p>IMP5 <i>Potential impact</i></p>	<p>This is filled in for all taxa regardless of whether information on the other impact questions (IMP1-4) is available. If no data is available on impacts in any introduced region of the <i>Species</i> and any closely related <i>Species</i>, use data from the native range of the <i>Species</i> and/or estimate the magnitude of impact possible for the <i>Species</i> in the <i>Area</i> based on its life history traits and trait based models for other taxa.</p> <p>In detail, estimate the potential of the <i>Species</i> to cause any impact in the magnitudes as described under IMP1 and IMP2 in the <i>Area</i>, including impacts for which no evidence has been recorded yet. Assume the <i>Species</i> is established and abundant in the <i>Area</i>, and consider the highest impact possible under any of the mechanisms and to any sector. Here we consider the life history traits of the <i>Species</i> which could lead to impact, including undesirable traits, as well as the recipient systems, meaning the recipient habitat and community. In some cases, impacts caused in the native range can be useful indicators of impact, for example impacts on agriculture.</p> <p>Undesirable traits include (but do not exclusively consist of): produces spines, thorns or burrs, allelopathic, parasitic, unpalatable to grazing animals, toxic to animals, host for recognised pests and pathogens, causes allergies or is otherwise toxic to humans, creates a fire hazard in natural ecosystems, grows on infertile soils, shade tolerant plant at some stage of its life cycle. Therefore these traits are likely to have an impact in the <i>Area</i> should it be invaded.</p> <p>Also consider here feeding habits, novelty aspects, functional traits, and studies performed on other groups and taxa considering trait-impact relationships.</p> <p>Potential impact</p> <p>Massive (MV) The <i>Species</i> is a transformer in its native range, has ecosystem engineering properties, or possesses other traits which suggest irreversible impacts on the community composition in the <i>Area</i> to occur. The <i>Species</i> is a pest of agricultural production in the native range and has the potential to cause irreversible losses of activities</p> <p>Major (MR) The <i>Species</i> has traits which suggest major impacts on native communities in the <i>Area</i>, but these impacts are likely to be reversible. The <i>Species</i> has traits which can lead to losses of activities</p> <p>Moderate (MO) The <i>Species</i> possesses several undesirable traits. Due to the traits of the <i>Species</i> and/or its behaviour, it is expected to reduce population sizes of at least one native species, and/or human well-being leading to people changing their activities</p> <p>Minor (MN) The <i>Species</i> does not possess any traits which could lead to effects on native species population sizes, but reduction in native individuals' performance is expected; and/or it could lead to loss in</p>

	<p>individual peoples' well-being and increased difficulties to perform normal activities. No changes to activity sizes</p> <p>Minimal Concern (MC) Due to the traits of the <i>Species</i> no effect on native individuals' performance is expected. No effects on human well-being are expected. The <i>Species</i> does not possess any undesirable traits</p>
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3.2.3. Risk score

As already indicated, the risk of the *Species* is calculated by the likelihood and maximum impact scores (Risk = Likelihood X Impact). Determine the overall risk score by highlighting the obtained likelihood of invasion and the maximum impact score of the *Species* in risk score table (Supplementary material 2). Record and communicate the risk score on the summary page.

3.3. Risk Management

Generally, the distinction between whether or not to manage a species relies on the risks it poses to the recipient environment. For species that are not yet present in a national park, and for which decisions on introduction or importation are required, this can be a relatively straightforward process: no new alien species are allowed in national parks and all efforts must be made to keep them out (see SANParks' Invasive and Alien Species Management Policy, Cole et al. 2018). This is not always feasible. If the Species poses a high risk it should be given priority attention, but if it is low risk, or is already in the *Area*, then if compared to the other major invasive alien species that require management, may form a low priority. However, decisions regarding species that are already present and potentially well established in an *Area*, and in use for various purposes, also depend on how easily they can be managed. Since management does not happen in isolation from the rest of society, social perceptions and benefits need to be assessed and accounted for in these cases, such as in the SANParks park management planning process. In National Parks, the main objectives of the park need to be assessed and carefully considered, and management should focus on preserving these benefits rather than the benefits of the alien species itself.

Furthermore, once a risk has been identified and assessed as a species of concern (i.e. medium or high risk), one needs to consider what can be done to manage the risk (e.g. Booy et al. 2017). For species already present in the *Area* where prevention is no longer an option this will often require a detailed evaluation of management options (e.g. Booy et al. 2020). The development of management plans needs to include financial resources, and a process of prioritisation of potential interventions, including budgetary considerations such as the funds available to put the management plan into action (Wilson et al. 2017; Canessa et al. 2021). Such needs are beyond the intended use of the RAAS framework as they also depend on policy decisions and allocation of resources, which is also dependant of the resources available across high priority species in other national parks. For example, the Working for Water/Biodiversity Social Projects, are required to balance the needs of 19 national parks, each with numerous high priority species, and also managing for other important goals (e.g. protecting endangered biome/vegetation types, water source areas). However, the framework provides for some basic management considerations that allow for a broad classification of how to treat a specific risk. Therefore, the aim of this section is to provide some guidance as to

which broad management goals should be investigated and which information is required in order to prioritise management actions. Further assessments should then be conducted on species assessed as high risk and the feasibility of management (success of control) is likely to be high, to further assess their priority for management in the specific area (e.g. Booy et al. 2017).

While the RAAS focusses on individual species, in the management prioritisation process different species are compared and weighted up against each other. In some cases, area based-management might be preferable to species focussed management (Downey & Sheppard 2006). In such an approach, low priority species would also be controlled if present in a specific area of interest. For example, in the case of alien plants, the Working for Water/Biodiversity Social Projects operate on a system of clearing species in designated areas (NBAL; Natural Biological Alien Land mapping code) in which the target species are listed. The lower/medium priority species may then be included as a target species within the standard clearing contracts.

The assessment of risk management generally is more open ended than the risk assessment (likelihood X impacts) which can be more quantitatively assessed. However, it needs to be documented in detail to assure transparency of decisions. In RAAS, this includes socio-economic and environmental benefits, the feasibility to stop future immigration of the Species and basic considerations regarding management feasibility. The latter are based on Wilson et al. (2017) and Panetta and Timmins (2004) and include a) accessibility of populations, b) whether the *Species* is hard to detect, c) time to reproduction, and d) propagule persistence of the *Species*. A scoring approach leads to a basic assessment of the ease of management.

Further to the assessment of these traits, it is important that for an assessment of eradication feasibility, a detailed study including, for example, the delimitation of all alien populations of the *Species* are needed. For example the extent of *Acacia paradoxa* in Table Mountain National Park and the potential for eradication thereof (Zenni et al. 2009). Determining population estimates and applying management trials for the European shore-crab (*Carcinus maenas*; Mabin et al. 2017). Eradication should not be set as a target if not evaluated in detail as this could lead to a waste of limited resources (e.g. Cacho et al. 2007). To aid this process, there is a question in the framework aimed at determining whether an extirpation or

eradication feasibility study has been performed for the *Area* (MAN4, Table 15), and a further questions on the range size (MAN5) and control options available (MAN6).

The answers provided in the risk management section feed into Figure 5, which leads to broad recommendations on how to manage a species. These differ based on whether the *Species* is already present in the *Area*, whether prevention or eradication are feasible goals. However, given these are only crude measures of management feasibility, further prioritisation needs to be done for the species which were assessed as high-risk and easy to medium management feasibility in RAAS.

Table 15: Questions and response options for the risk management section of the analysis.

MAN question number	Question / information required
<p>MAN1 <i>What is the feasibility to stop future invasion into the Area?</i></p>	<p>Assess here if future immigration of the <i>Species</i> into the <i>Area</i> can be prevented. If the <i>Species</i> is already present (see BAC10), this is needed to determine whether eradication is a feasible goal. If the <i>Species</i> is not yet in the <i>Area</i> this determines whether prevention is a feasible goal. Based on the pathways identified in BAC14 and the answers provided in LIK1 and LIK2, estimate the feasibility to stop propagules from entering the <i>Area</i>.</p> <p>Response options: High: The <i>Species</i> is introduced into the <i>Area</i> intentionally with pathways which are easier to regulate and control; e.g. ornamental plants in staff and camp gardens, pets, aquaria. Low: The <i>Species</i> is introduced into the <i>Area</i> unintentionally, for example as contaminant and stowaway, and/or is present in neighbouring countries and areas and is entering the <i>Area</i> unaided. Bear in mind parks within a mixed urban/park landscape have multiple pathways and porous borders.</p>
<p>MAN2 <i>Benefits of the Species</i></p>	<p>Species with significant benefits and significant costs (impacts) are sometimes termed conflict species. The benefits might be in terms of either socio-economy or the environment. Crucially the benefits of an introduction are often spatially and temporally separated from the costs of an invasion. This section (MAN2a & MAN2b) aims at assessing current socio-economic and environmental benefits to highlight potential conflicts of interest. Stakeholders might need to be consulted to answer these questions (see also Novoa et al. 2018), this may include the SANParks park management planning process, other external stakeholders and internal stakeholders. Summarise the current benefits using the maximum of both, socio-economic and environmental benefits as outlines below. Keep in mind that conflicts are expected especially if socio-economic benefits are significant. If relevant, mention potential benefits here, but base your response on actual, current benefits.</p>

<p>MAN2a Socio-economic benefits of the Species</p>	<p>Socio-economic benefits, if appropriate, should be described to ensure an objectivity and recognition of the services that may be provided by the <i>Species</i>. Under Rational and comments, list the benefits and the significance of each. Include here if the <i>Species</i> is used for any of the following: as pet, in horticulture, for fencing, shading, dune stabilisation, firewood, building material, hunting, fishing, human food, animal feed and fodder, fabric production, etc. Benefits are rated as of high or low significance, based on the criteria outlined below. Details of the benefits and why they are rated in the respective level need to be provided in the Rationale.</p> <p>High: Significant benefits are expected if the <i>Species</i> provides a service or makes an activity possible which is not available without the <i>Species</i>, i.e., which is not provided by the native species in the <i>Area</i>. Also covered here are services provided by the <i>Species</i> which are essential for security, adequate livelihoods, sufficient nutritious food, access to clean air and water, and food, e.g. plants grown for food at ranger outposts.</p> <p>Low: List benefits which can be easily relatively replaced by a native, e.g. horticultural plants, trees for shade. Depending on the size of the affected area/park, conflicts are still possible therefore it is important to outline these benefits regardless. Also covered here are services provided by the <i>Species</i> which affect aspects of human well-being related to social, spiritual and cultural relations. These need to be well documented as important issues in parks, for example in the park management plan.</p>
<p>MAN2b Environmental benefits of the Species</p>	<p>Here, benefits to the natural environment and native species in the <i>Area</i> are assessed. Benefits are rated as of high or low significance, based on the criteria outlined below. Details of the benefits and why they are rated in the respective level need to be provided in the Rationale, and especially considered in the context of SANParks' objectives.</p> <p>High: High benefits are expected if the <i>Species</i> provides a crucial habitat or food source to an environment. Ideally these functions should be replaceable over time by native species, but it indicates that current control would be detrimental to conservation or ecosystem functioning. Significant benefits are also noted if the <i>Species</i> provides resources which are not or no longer available without the <i>Species</i> present to native species, especially to rare, endemic or threatened species. It is expected that there will be few such examples and they would, where possible, form part of a rehabilitation plan (in the park management plan or other park rehabilitation plans, e.g. Biodiversity Social Projects).</p> <p>Low: Benefits to native species and ecosystems which can relatively easily be replaced by another (native or non-harmful alien) <i>Species</i>.</p>
<p>MAN3 Ease of management</p>	<p>Some invasions or species are notoriously difficult to control, and this influences both the decisions concerning risk management and how the risks should be communicated. Values as described in MAN3a-MAN3d are assigned for situations where the <i>Species</i> has been detected, not where it could be found, in the <i>Area</i>. This is only relevant if the <i>Species</i> is present in the <i>Area</i> (BAC10). Provide detailed answers to MAN3a-MAN3d</p>

	<p>in the Answer sheet and calculate the ease of management, i.e. the sum of the answers.</p> <p>Response options: >5: Difficult. Generally difficult to manage (e.g. specialist equipment or techniques are required / multiple approaches are needed for control to be effective / management is an expensive operation over several seasons) 3–5: Medium. Some aspects make it more difficult to manage <3: Easy. Management is relatively straightforward (e.g. can be achieved without substantial training or repeated control efforts)</p>
<p>MAN3a How accessible are populations?</p>	<p>Rate how easily accessible the populations of the <i>Species</i> are in the <i>Area</i>. Base your response on the most difficult to access. Moderately accessible will include regions that pose some operational difficulty, but that might not necessarily require specialised teams (e.g. a riparian area), and private gardens. To be rated as difficult to access, the <i>Species</i>' distribution must involve at least some sites that are very difficult to access (e.g. a ravine or cliff requiring rope access).</p> <p>Response options: 0 for easy access 1 for moderately accessible 2 for difficult to access; or don't know</p>
<p>MAN3b Is the <i>Species</i> hard to detect?</p>	<p>Assess if the <i>Species</i> is easily detectable during the year (response: no) or if it is only detectable during certain seasons or time-periods (response: yes). The objective of this question is to distinguish species that are readily detectable throughout the year from those that might be detectable only for short periods (e.g. following the production of new foliage or as dispersing adults). Select yes if it is never easily detectable. If the <i>Species</i> is detectable relatively briefly it provides only small windows for control prior to reproductive events, as well as planning for surveillance and monitoring to be suitably planned.</p> <p>Response options: 0 for no. 1 for partially or for most of the year. 2 for yes; or only detectable for a few weeks a year; or don't know.</p>
<p>MAN3c Time to reproduction</p>	<p>Assess the time the <i>Species</i> takes from being juvenile to a reproductive stage (e.g. for animals how long does it take from being born to reproducing?). It will be more difficult to prevent reproduction of a <i>Species</i> that reproduces quickly than those that have extended juvenile periods. Default value (i.e. if unknown) is 1.</p> <p>Response options: 0 for > 3 years 1 for 1–3 years; or don't know 2 for < 1 year</p>
<p>MAN3d Propagule persistence</p>	<p>Describe here how long resting stages, seeds, spores, fragments, eggs, or other parts of the <i>Species</i> can stay/persist in an environment before they die and are not able to progress to adult stages. Propagule persistence is often one of the most important impediments to control,</p>

	<p>since it sets the minimum duration for an eradication programme. Default value if unknown is 1.</p> <p>Response options: 0 for < 1 year 1 for 1–5 years; or don't know 3 for > 5 years</p>						
<p>MAN4 Has the feasibility of extirpation or eradication been evaluated in the Area, other SANParks, or similar protected areas (ideally with similar habitat or in the same biome) that may provide insights for the Area being assessed?</p>	<p>Determining whether eradication or extirpation is a feasible goal is a process in and of itself, and while it requires some of the information that is used elsewhere in this framework [e.g. whether it is feasible to stop future immigration (MAN1), and the overall ease of management (MAN3)], it also requires a large amount of other information. Much of this information will only become available as control efforts are piloted (see Wilson et al. 2017 for detailed guidelines for evaluating eradication feasibility and monitoring progress). A detailed evaluation of extirpation/eradication feasibility will ideally include: explicit delimitation of populations (to gain an indication of spatial extent), trial management, an assessment of current status, a risk map, a bioeconomic / decision support model showing costs and potential success of different control scenarios (e.g. Moore et al. 2011), and a proposed management strategy with time-lines and specific goals.</p> <p>Response options: Yes: there has been a detailed evaluation of extirpation/eradication feasibility that has been documented (e.g. in a journal article). No: there has been no evaluation of extirpation/eradication for the Area or a different region.</p>						
<p>MAN5 What is the range size of Species in the Area?</p>	<p>Estimate the range size of the Species within the Area. This is crucial for Species that are potentially easy to manage based on MAN3. The difference between range sizes will help to distinguish between High and Medium priority. Species that are potentially difficult to manage are considered low priority regardless of their range size.</p> <p>Response options: Isolated individuals, patches or populations Small range size: <10 % Medium range size: ≥10 % but ≤20 % Large range size: >20 %</p>						
<p>MAN6 What are the control options and management actions available for the Species?</p>	<p>Describe here management actions taken and control options available for the Species. If known, add information on eradication and control attempts in the Area, number of populations, distribution in hectares, and other information which can feed into control plans and/or eradication feasibility studies for the Area. Include measures taken in the Area currently and historically, and elsewhere. Include ongoing or future plans for biocontrol, herbicides registered, control trials, etc. Include information on the success of each method, if known. At a broad level, use the following guidance adapted from those developed for the Global Invasive Species Database (GISD). More specific details should be taken from the park management plans and other SANParks specific documents.</p> <p>Categories of management actions for alien species</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Management</th> <th>Definition</th> <th>Management sub-category</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Management	Definition	Management sub-category			
Management	Definition	Management sub-category					

	category	
	Monitoring	Measures taken to evaluate the distribution, expansion and/or density of the <i>Species</i> .
	Prevention	Measures taken to stop the <i>Species</i> from entering an area.
	Eradication/extirpation	Actions taken to eliminate all occurrences of the <i>Species</i> . Long term, on-going eradication projects are included in this category.
	Control	Measures taken to reduce the <i>Species</i> or biomass (control), to keep the <i>Species</i> in a defined area (containment), and/or to reduce harmful effects of the <i>Species</i> (mitigation).
	None Unknown	
		Best practises Cultural methods Shooting Trapping Hand removal Pesticides or herbicides Poisoning or toxicants Others (disease, fumigants, draining...) Physical-Mechanical (manual) Chemical Biological Integrated methods
MAN7 Any other management considerations to highlight?	This is intended to support those tasked with decision making, so a critical evaluation of options (including those that are not suitable) is useful, but it should ideally be backed up with appropriate referencing. It might also include information useful for management prioritisation or that might ultimately end up in a species-specific management plan.	

3.4. Risk Communication

Once the level of risk has been determined and options for management and benefits evaluated, it is crucial to clearly communicate the outcomes of the analysis to relevant stakeholders, which in the context of SANParks include: Working for Water/Biodiversity Social Projects, park managers/rangers/conservation managers, regional ecologists, relevant scientists and other stakeholders. Risk communication is important to provide the stakeholders with sufficient information to understand the outcomes of the risk assessment and recommendations, and be in a position to know under which circumstances particular decisions are needed. Therefore, communication needs to be clear enough to reach a common understanding, and needs to provide enough information to underpin the decision in a transparent manner.

In the RAAS framework we incorporated several communication strategies to reach these goals. We provide a decision tree (Figure 5) which uses information from the analysis to make recommendations on the management strategy for the *Species*. This depicts a simplified decision-making process which can be easily understood by policy makers and stakeholders generally, while the details to feed into the flow diagram are documented and provided in detail during the full assessment process. The

summary page (Figure 1) highlights the important findings from the full assessment, including the conclusions from each section, with short descriptions on the *Species* itself, impacts, risks, ease of management and benefits.

A decision tree can be used in recommending an appropriate course of action (Figure 5), based on the outcomes of the risk assessment. The decisions reached after the full assessment can provide some insights into recommendations that may be made in the risk analysis summary page.

While decision trees are commonly used tools to provide some level of guidance, they do not always require a comprehensive set of data to support each of the steps and thus might suffer from bias. By completing the risk analysis detailed, evidence based data provides the necessary information to assist in making a particular decision. The decision tree provides information on the area under consideration, overall risk, as determined by the likelihood X impact scores and ease of management used to determine management priorities and options.

Use the decision tree to determine the recommended goal and the *Species'* level of priority to indicate the outcomes in the table below (Table 16). Justify the recommendations and provide a well-motivated, credible and evidence based summary in the summary page. Highlight the current listing category of the species under the NEMBA A&IS Regulations. Provide recommendations on further studies needed, management plans, stakeholder engagement, etc.

Table 16: Information to be included for the recommended goal and priority level.

<p>Recommended goal:</p> <p>The recommendation goals must be based on the overall risk, ease of management score, and the estimated range size, while taking into account other factors from the analysis. The recommended goal will then determine the species' level of priority for the national park (i.e. on the right column). The recommended goal will be one of the following:</p> <p>Potential eradication target: based on medium to high overall risk score, an 'easy'</p>	<p>National park priority level:</p> <p>A process separate from this risk analysis is needed to evaluate whether eradication is a feasible goal. This will insure that limited resources are used in a strategic manner. The risk analysis will help in determining species that should be prioritized for this process. Thus the recommended priority level of in the risk analysis will be one of the following:</p> <p>High priority: Should receive immediate management attention. These are species</p>
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<p>ease of management and small estimated range size. Requires urgent eradication feasibility assessment including distribution surveys -finding all individuals, cost / budgeting, rapid response control strategy, and a long-term sustained control programme. This includes species listed under Category 1a in the NEMBA A&S Regulations.</p> <p>Potential containment target: based on a medium to high overall risk score, an 'easy' ease of management score, and a medium to large range size. Eradication unlikely, but same as above generally; aim at the population level (contain and reduce the abundance of the population).</p> <p>Long-term control programme: based on medium to high overall risk, and 'difficult to medium' score under ease of management. Schedule into future clearing project cycles/contracts.</p> <p>Monitoring/surveillance: Surveillance/distribution and assessing trends. This includes species with low overall risk; species that are not yet present in the park but have high feasibility for future immigration.</p>	<p>recommended as "potential eradication targets". Emerging species (very small population) at a national level and within the park. Species listed under category 1a of the national regulations are automatically high priority (require eradication plans under any scenario).</p> <p>Medium priority: not legible for an eradication feasibility evaluation but populations should be monitored. These are mostly species recommended as a "potential containment target".</p> <p>Low priority: Do not prioritise for eradication or management/control. These are species recommended for "long-term control programme".</p> <p>Not priority: Do not consider for prioritization. These are species recommended for monitoring or surveillance.</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p>Outline the recommendation and reasons for arriving at this, i.e. motivate your reasoning to arrive at this conclusion. This should also include recommendations on further studies needed, management plans, stakeholder engagement, etc. Note what the current listing category is under the NEMBA A&S Regulations (include the current date/version of the published regulations, as well as what the category means).</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p>Outline the recommendation and reasons for arriving at this, i.e. motivate your reasoning to arrive at this conclusion. The decision tree (Figure 5) can provide some insight into further actions</p>

4. CONCLUSION

The aim of RAAS is to provide a robust approach to conducting risk analysis including in-depth risk assessments and basic considerations of risk management which can be easily conducted without requiring expert knowledge. While science–management interactions vary by park or region, the outcome of the analysis needs to be communicated to the relevant management authority for further consideration. This may be done through science-management forums, or, as in the case of Kruger NP, the Conservation Services Management Committee. At the same time the relevant Working for Water/Biodiversity Social Project cluster or project managers should be informed in order to determine whether (and how) the risk analysis outcomes may be used for future project planning.

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Appendix

Appendix 1: Sources of information

Examples of sources for information that may be useful to consult in completing the assessment. This is not an exhaustive list, but provides a starting point on where to search for information that can be used for the risk analysis.

Many of the scientific journals listed below require a subscription to access the articles (although some individual articles are open access), which unfortunately SANParks does not have, however many of the articles can be requested directly from the authors who will usually provide the reprint willingly. Google Scholar is a scientific reference search engine and can find many of the articles needed (<https://scholar.google.co.za>). Additionally, consider atlases and other distribution databases, like for example SABAP2 (Southern African Bird Atlas Project; <http://sabap2.adu.org.za/>), SAPIA, the Red List of Threatened Species (<http://www.iucnredlist.org/>), and other databases on alien species (e.g. <http://www.griis.org/>; <http://www.europe-aliens.org/>).

SANParks' Park Management Plans and related documents may provide information on the species being assessed, as to whether the Species is in or near the park, if and what management is planned or being done, names/synonyms, and other aspects of the risk assessment.

Species/group	Source	Source type	Reference
All	SANParks Park Management Plans	Park Plan	https://www.sanparks.org/conservation/park_man/approved_plans.php
All	SANParks State of Knowledge Reports	Biodiversity Reports	https://www.sanparks.org/scientific-services/data-information-resources/state-of-knowledge-reports
All	The status of biological invasions and their management in South Africa in 2017	Report (2018) on the status of biological invasions in South Africa	Van Wilgen BW & Wilson JR (Eds.) (2018) http://biodiversityadvisor.sanbi.org/planning-and-assessment/invasive-alien-species-status-report/
All	The status of biological invasions and their management in South Africa in 2019	Report (2020) on the status of biological invasions in South Africa	Zengeya TA & Wilson JR (eds.) (2020) http://biodiversityadvisor.sanbi.org/planning-and-assessment/invasive-alien-species-status-report/
All	Biological Invasions in South Africa	Open access book. Provides an encyclopaedic overview of all aspects of	van Wilgen BW, Measey M, Richardson DM, Wilson JR & Zengeya TA (2020) https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-030-32394-3

Species/ group	Source	Source type	Reference
		biological invasions in South Africa	
Plants	Hawaiian Ecosystems at Risk (HEAR): Risk Assessments	Website	http://www.org/wra/
All	Austral Ecology	Peer-reviewed journal with many papers on invasive species	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/14429993
All	Biodiversity and Conservation	Peer-reviewed journal with many papers on invasive species	https://www.springer.com/journal/10531
Plants	Hawaiian Ecosystems at Risk (HEAR): Risk Assessment	Website	http://www.hear.org/wra/
All	Austral Ecology	Peer-review journal with many papers on invasive species	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/14429993
All	Biodiversity and Conservation	Peer-review journal with many papers on invasive species	https://www.springer.com/content/0960-3115/
All	BioInvasion Records	Peer-review journal with many papers on invasive species	http://www.reabic.net/journals/bir/2012/Issue1.aspx
All	Biological Conservation	Peer-review journal with many papers on invasive species	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/journal/00063207
All	Biological Invasions	Peer-review journal with many papers on invasive species	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1111/(i002/9781118223130.ch20
All	CABI Crop Protection Compendium	Website	http://www.cabi.org/cpc/
All	CABI Invasive Species Compendium	Website	http://www.cabi.org/isc/
All	Conservation Biology	Peer-review journal with many papers on invasive species	Peer-review journal with many papers on invasive species
All	Delivering Alien Invasive Species Inventories for Europe (DAISIE)	Website	www.europe-aliens.org
All	Diversity and Distribution	Peer-review journal with many papers on invasive species	http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/10.1111/(ISSN)1472-4642
All	Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)	Website	http://www.gbif.org/
All	Global Invasive Species Database (GISD)	Website	http://www.issg.org/database/welcome
All	Hawaiian Ecosystem at Risk (HEAR)	Website	http://www.hear.org/
All	Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS)	Website	http://www.itis.gov/
All	Invasive Alien Species Indicators	Website	http://academic.sun.ac.za/iasii/

Species/ group	Source	Source type	Reference
All	North European and Baltic Network on Invasive Alien Species (NOBANIS)	Website	http://www.nobanis.org
Amphibians	Amphibian web	Website	http://amphibiaweb.org/
Aquatic plants	Aquatic Plant Information System Online (APIS)	Website	http://el.erdc.usace.army.mil/aqual/apis/Intro.aspx
Aquatic plants	Aquatic Invasions Research Directory	Website	http://invasions.si.edu/aird
Aquatic plants	Database on Introductions of Aquatic Species (DAIS)	Website	http://www.fao.org/fishery/dias/en
Aquatic	Nonindigenous Aquatic Species	Website	http://nas.er.usgs.gov/
Plants	Invasive plants of the World	Website	https://powo.science.kew.org/
Plants	A new comprehensive database of alien plant species in Chile based on herbarium records	Primary Literature Supplementary Material	Fuentes et al. (2012)
Reptiles	A quantitative climate-match score for risk assessment screening of reptile and amphibian introductions	Primary Literature	Van Wilgen et al. (2009)
Reptiles	The reptile database	Website	http://www.reptile-database.org
Reptiles and Amphibians	Alien reptiles and amphibians, a scientific compendium and analyses	Reference Book	Kraus (2009)
Arthropods	North American Non-Indigenous Arthropod Database (NANIAD)	Website	http://www.invasivespecies.org.NA/NIAD.html
Birds	Introduced birds of the world: the worldwide history, distribution, and influence of birds introduced to new environments	Reference Book	Long (1981)
Birds	Naturalized birds of the world	Reference Book	Lever (1987)
Freshwater Fish	FishBase	Website	http://fishbase.org/search.php
Freshwater Fish	Naturalized fishes of the world	Reference Book	Lever (1996)
Freshwater species	A handbook of global freshwater invasive species	Reference Book	Francis (2011)
Mammals	Introduced mammals of the world: their history, distribution, and influence	Primary Literature	Long (2003)
Mammals	Mammal Species of the World. A Taxonomic and Geographic Reference	Primary Literature	Wilson & Reeder (2005)

Species/ group	Source	Source type	Reference
Mammals	Naturalized mammals of the world	Reference Book	Lever (1985)
Marine and Freshwater species	National Exotic Marine and Estuarine Species Information System (NEMESIS)	Website	http://invasions.si.edu/nemesis/
Marine species	Database of Global Marine Invasive Species Threats	Primary Literature: Supplementary Material	Molnar et al. (2008)
Marine species	The Baltic Sea Alien Species Database	Website	http://www.corpi.ku.lt/nemo/
Marine species		Website	http://www.marinespecies.org/
Plants	A global compendium of weeds	Reference Book	Randal et al. (2021)
Plants	Australia's Virtual Herbarium	Website	http://avh.ala.org.au
Plants	CalFlora	Website	http://www.calflora.org/

Appendix 2: Pathway categories and sub-categories

Pathway categories to consider during the assessment of the *Species'* primary (BAC14, LIK1, and LIK 2) and secondary introduction (LIK5 and LIK6). The categories and subcategories are based on those accepted by the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (see also Essl et al. 2011), and aligns with the Pathway Controlled Vocabulary List of Terms.

Category	Subcategory
RELEASE IN NATURE	Biological control
	Erosion control/ dune stabilization (windbreaks, hedges...)
	Fishery in the wild
	Hunting in the wild
	Landscape/flora/fauna improvement
	Conservation introduction
	Release in nature for use (other than above, e.g. medical use, fur..)
	Other Intentional release
ESCAPE FROM CONFINEMENT	Agriculture (including biofuel feedstocks)
	Aquaculture/mariculture
	Botanical garden/zoo/aquaria (excluding domestic aquaria)
	Farmed animals
	Forestry
	Fur farms
	Horticulture
	Ornamental purpose other than horticulture
	Pet/aquarium/terrarium species
	Research (in facilities)
	Live food and live bait
	Other escape from confinement
TRANSPORT – CONTAMINANT	Contaminant nursery material
	Contaminated bait
	Food contaminant
	Contaminant on animals (except species transported by host/vector)
	Contaminant on plants (except species transported by host/vector)
	Parasites on animals
	Parasites on plants
	Seed contaminant
	Timber trade
	Transportation of habitat material (soil, vegetation...)

TRANSPORT – STOWAWAY	Angling/fishing aquaculture equipment
	Container/bulk
	Hitchhikers in or on plane
	Hitchhikers on ship/boat
	Machinery/equipment
	People and their luggage/equipment
	Ship/boat ballast water
	Ship/boat hull fouling
	Vehicles (car, trains...)
	Other means of transport
CORRIDOR	Interconnected waterways/basins/seas
	Tunnels and land bridges
UNAIDED	<p>Natural dispersal across borders of alien species that have been introduced into the donor region through pathways 1 to 5</p> <p>Introduction without direct anthropogenic influence from an adjacent area where the <i>Taxon</i> is alien</p>